

**D4.31 Final reports of JIP
COVRIN and OHEJP exercise
(SimEx) and evaluation
reports**

**WP4 – Joint Integrative
Projects**

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FINAL REPORTS OF JIP COVRIN AND OHEJP EXERCISE (SIMEX) AND EVALUATION REPORTS

Introduction

In December of 2019 a new coronavirus started to spread in China. The virus was named severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). In a couple of months this novel virus had spread to other areas of Asia and globally. The World Health Organisation (WHO) declared the outbreak pandemic in March 2020. Very soon it became known that feline animals could get infected and also get a disease similar to the human disease. SARS-CoV-2 also spread rapidly among farmed minks, showing several animals to be competent hosts for the infection. As it became obvious that animals could get infected by SARS-CoV-2, the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP) decided to set up a project to tackle a set of urgent research questions related to this coronavirus. The OHEJP Joint Integrative Project JIP06-COVRIN was approved. The project started in March 2021 with a duration of 2 years.

Another need that became obvious as the OHEJP progressed was the need to train the new skills developed within the programme. Originally there was a topic, IA 2.4: Sharing best intervention practice – twinning and simulation exercises, in the second call for JIPs. This topic addressed the action step in the prevent-detect-respond chain of the Integrative Strategy Matrix (see Figure 1), but no project proposal was submitted. The OHEJP Scientific Steering Board (SSB) thus decided to allocate some of the budget for the missing project to a simulation exercise, which could also contribute to training the new skills developed within the programme. After consultations with ECDC and EFSA an OHEJP exercise (SimEx) was set up. The exercise was cross-sectorial and was designed to be conducted nationally. It was voluntary for the OHEJP partners to participate. Eleven countries decided to join the exercise and in most countries all the three sectors, Public Health, Animal Health and Food Safety were engaged.

This report is on the final reports and evaluations of these two projects.

Figure 1: The JIP COVRIN aligned with several steps in the OHEJP Integrative Strategy Matrix and SimEx mainly addressed the Action step.

The projects have delivered a set of outputs that are all publically available according to the Open Access policy of the Horizon 2020 framework programme. COVRIN has, so far, provided 58 deliverables and 14 scientific publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals. The deliverables and publications are available through Zenodo, the chosen official repository of the One Health EJP. SimEx was a bit differently organised than the JIPs and provided one deliverable and one peer-reviewed publication. In addition, a popular science article is under preparation.

A summary of the outputs from both projects can be found in the current document and many outputs can also be found in a searchable way in the One Health EJP [Outcome Inventory](https://c1abo859.caspio.com/dp/e05d7000137f7c9dd846442f83fcon) <https://c1abo859.caspio.com/dp/e05d7000137f7c9dd846442f83fcon> on the OHEJP website.

The two main integrative research objectives of COVRIN were to identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV2 and to generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV2. Among other things, genome detection assays and serological tests have been evaluated for harmonization as have sampling procedures. Risk factors for pet-human transmission have been assessed and coronavirus has been screened in various animal species. Risk assessment models of coronavirus in animals have been established.

In the OHEJP exercise, SimEx, the One Health capability, capacity and interoperability of authorities in Public Health, Animal Health and Food Safety to work together was tested. More than 20 partners from 11 European countries participated. A scenario with a foodborne outbreak involving all participating sectors was set up. Focus was on collaboration, roles and responsibilities during a zoonotic outbreak and understanding the benefits of a One Health perspective, especially when it comes to collecting and sharing data. Communication skills were also trained and the importance of creating a common main message was emphasised. After the exercise recommendations building on the experiences from SimEx were created as were recommendations for future One Health exercises.

The outputs from the projects have been widely disseminated, both within the OHEJP, to the OHEJP main stakeholders and to national stakeholders. In addition, there have been requests for the scenario, created by the SimEx project team.

For each of the two projects, a final report has been provided. These have been evaluated following the D4.19 “Guidelines for evaluation of final Joint Integrative Projects and SimEx Project” - the guidelines are available as an appendix at the end of this report. Each of the final reports has been evaluated by three different, external, independent scientific evaluators.

For COVRIN the evaluators have assessed the alignment of the project results with the initial objectives as described in the full proposal, the scientific excellence and the innovative approach of the project, the quality and efficiency of the implementation, whether the research project has delivered integrative activities and One Health aspects, whether the results contain elements for sustainability, and finally what the expected impact of the project may be. For the evaluation of SimEx the original evaluation scheme was modified to better align with the objectives of SimEx. The comments are very valuable and have been forwarded to the project leaders for further dissemination within the respective project. The evaluators are kept anonymous in the correspondence with the project leaders and in this report. All evaluators have received detailed instructions with an extensive description of the criteria and guidance for scoring. Still, the scaling may be interpreted differently by the evaluators.

COVRIN scored 19.7 in total, which means scoring more than 3 as an average for all criteria, where 3 is equal to “Very good”. In case of a lower score for a specific criterion, the evaluator has given the reasons for this in the comment. The evaluators find the project scientifically sound and of high quality. They especially mention the many innovative approaches that were successfully used in the project. The consortium of scientists was well integrated and they were able to share data and contribute to a joint approach for surveillance etc. There are some doubts about the sustainability of the outputs, since scientists will move on to other projects and the use of the new methods are dependent on factors that cannot be controlled by the project. However, the One Health impact of the project is highlighted, especially since data already have been used by EFSA in risk assessments.

The evaluation of SimEx resulted in a total score of 23.0, which is equal to an average score of 4 for all criteria. This is equal to “Excellent”. The evaluators found the results to be well aligned with the project objectives. The scenario, based on a foodborne zoonotic outbreak, challenged authorities from different sectors to communicate and work together. They also found the exercises very well organized and the different roles and responsibilities of different players were well defined and communicated. The development of a clear outline and guide on how to develop and conduct exercises is suggested by one of the evaluators for further sustainability of the project outcome. The impact of the project is considerable and will very likely have positive secondary effects especially on collaboration and communication between the sectors. The results will contribute to building stronger strategies and action plans in crisis management.

In addition an in-depth analysis on actions taken and lessons learned in SimEx has been performed by a fellow of the ECDC programme on Field Epidemiology and Public Health Microbiology (EPIET/EUPHEM). The analysis is based on the documentation of SimEx activities and complemented with interviews with representatives for the different sectors PH/AH/FS in four participating countries. The focus is on how the different sectors perceived the exercise. One conclusion of the analysis is that countries seeking to improve their One Health strategy, should prioritize to establish a routine of meetings with representatives from different sectors. The full in-depth analysis can be found in Appendix I.

Projects final reports and evaluations

In this document, the final reports are followed by their evaluation, respectively. The names of the evaluators are removed from the reports to guarantee the confidentiality of the process.

The sections relating to ethics (only relevant for COVRIN) and DMP from the original reports were not included in this document because they both refer only to information exchange (with the ethics advisors or with OHEJP WP4 regarding DMP) and not to the scientific or technical results, and therefore have no influence on the evaluation of the project.

The anonymised evaluation reports were shared with the project leaders as support for their further work. The One Health EJP Project Management Team will not take any particular initiative with respect to a specific project evaluation, but will focus on the deliverables obtained and their dissemination to the interested stakeholders.

Final Report JIP06-COVRIN: SARS-CoV-2 Research Integration and Preparedness

1. Summary of the work carried out in the Project

Research and integration activities in the One Health EJP COVRIN project, have achieved the two main overall operational objectives: A) to identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV-2, B) to generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV-2.

In the research area of work package 1, Detection of SARS-CoV-2 in animal reservoirs and the environment, data of SARS-CoV-2 genome testing were shared, and immunoassays methodologies were shared and harmonized. A ring-trial of tests was completed, with recommendations implemented in national and international reference laboratories allowing assessment of potential hosts of SARS-CoV-2. In the tasks on assessment of bioavailability, association between detection of the virus genome, and its ability to be infectious was assessed providing crucial information for risk assessment.

In work package 2 on SARS-CoV-2 characterization, genome analyses and next generation sequencing of detected isolates and metagenomic sequencing of different samples were undertaken. Surveys were executed to make a summary description of protocols and to make an overview of the key steps of the bioinformatics analyses. A bioinformatics ring trial was undertaken to harmonize bioinformatics pipelines. Regarding *in vitro* and *ex vivo* biological characterization of circulating SARS-CoV-2 strains, cell line models have been collated and shared between partners. These will allow better analyses of virus traits related to zoonotic and/or reverse zoonotic transmission.

In work package 3 on SARS-CoV-2 risk assessment and surveillance, formats and procedures for sampling and surveillance in wildlife, livestock and pets and the environment were evaluated and reported. These were augmented by workshops to involve partners in the surveillance data collection. A review of surveillance activities in the different countries was produced. Risk factors for virus transmission in wildlife reservoirs, food producing animals and the environment are being studied and analyses of transmissions in pets were produced. An overview with a One Health perspective of models and parameters to assess transmission in animals was reported.

In work package 4 of COVRIN on coronavirus preparedness, detection of virus from different wildlife species were performed. A report on relevant sample types and hot spots for coronavirus sampling was produced to evaluate the impact of ecological factors and interventions. These outputs are aimed at identification of drivers of virus emergence through evaluation of phylodynamic and cross-species interactions with focus on zoonotic and reverse zoonotic aspects and adaptations. Capacity built, data generated, and research outcomes will be used in future national programmes and collaborative networks to develop control strategies, intervention strategies and prevention.

2. Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP0 - Coordination

JIP06-WP0-T0.1 - Internal project organization (M40 – M63)

ST0.1.1 – Development of share-point for data exchange (M40 – M42)

A SharePoint for data exchange of the different work packages has been constructed and included in the COVRIN website. The COVRIN group SharePoint can be accessed by all researchers within the COVRIN network and was used throughout the project.

Deliverable D0.1.1 Share-point for data exchange of the different work packages – **completed and in use by partners.**

ST0.1.2 – Management reporting year 1 (M40 – M51)

Each work package in the COVRIN project was assigned a work package leader and a deputy work package leader, who between them coordinated all activities and acted as a contact point for the coordinators. Furthermore, individual task leaders were assigned which facilitated the rapid communication between WP coordinators as those carrying out the planned tasks in the project. As the task leaders changed during the project a spreadsheet containing the contact details was created and regularly updated. Meetings within the work packages were held as regularly as required to ensure a smooth running of the activities. In these meetings discussion of work progress, including delivery of the planned deliverables. Due to all partners involvement in their national COVID-19 responses some deliverables had to be postponed or merged. No deliverables were cancelled.

Personnel changes throughout the project did result in some issues, particularly in the early stages before the list was created as not all changes were directly communicated with the coordinators and not in all cases the task was taken over by another task leader. The most serious impact was with the management plan but minimised to a delay in submission.

Deliverable D0.1.2: First management report:
<https://zenodo.org/record/7445670#.Y5wqOnbMJPY>.

ST0.1.3 – Management reporting year 2 (M52 – M63)

The setup of the COVRIN project with a coordinator, a deputy coordinator and 5 work package leaders worked very well. Changes in WP leaders and task leaders resulted in some hampering in the execution of the tasks and in the late completion of a few of the deliverables. Especially because of the hard work and the flexibility of the coordinators and some of the WP leaders or deputies, problems could be solved. As in year 1 several deliverables had to be postponed. All deliverables were completed, and all outputs described in the work plan delivered by the end of the project.

Deliverable D0.1.3 Second management report:
<https://zenodo.org/record/7778055#.ZCLckXZByUk>

JIP06-WP0-T0.2 - Communication and reporting (M40 – M63)

ST0.2.1 – Communications reporting year 1 (M40 – M51)

The COVRIN project page and group were set up on the OHEJP website. A comprehensive list of contact details for each work package, task and subtask has been compiled and uploaded to the secure area of the OHEJP website and is in use for organising meetings and compiling reports.

No communications officer was appointed to the COVRIN project, the majority of communications was done by the COVRIN coordinator and deputy supported where possible by the OHEJP communications team and several of the partner communication officers.

Communication activities in the first half year of the COVRIN project began with internal communications within the EJP One Health network.

- OHEJP Project Management Team (PMT)
- Project Owner Committee (POC)
- Scientific Steering Board (SSB)
- External Scientific Advisory Board (ESAB)
- Stakeholder Committee (SC)

COVRIN stakeholders were also updated by circulating an executive summary of the annual reports of the project.

COVRIN research outcomes were also presented during several scientist network meetings and conferences.

- STAR-IDAZ
- PREZODE program meeting
- European Society of Veterinary Virology meeting.
- UK International Coronavirus network (UK CoVnet)

COVRIN played an important role in the UK CoVnet both as an advisor and by assisting the organisation of network meetings.

Deliverable D0.2.1: First annual communications report: <https://zenodo.org/record/7448604>

ST0.2.2 – Communications reporting year 2 (M52 – M63)

COVRIN communication activities during the second year of the project consisted of several internal and external presentations about the project progress and outcomes. This included presentations for OHEJP internal bodies and project funders and stakeholders. Overall, COVRIN presentations were again well received.

Deliverable D0.2.2 Second Annual communications report:
<https://zenodo.org/record/7778068>

JIP06-WP0-T0.3 - Meetings and stakeholder connections (M40 – M66)

ST0.3.1 – Scoping exercise on related projects (M40 – M45)

The scoping exercise to avoid overlaps with other EU funded projects on Covid-19 has been completed. The exercise delivered a database identifying 63 SARS-CoV-2 initiatives (consortia), 28 other relevant initiatives, 9 COVID-19 data and laboratory-related efforts, and 17 Research Infrastructures (including 2 SARS-CoV-2 initiative duplicate entries).

The database has been published in Zenodo (see deliverable link below). In general, most identified research activities focus on human SARS-CoV-2 infections or COVID-19 disease with limited research activities specifically targeting SARS-CoV-2 in animals and the environment.

This scoping review of EU-supported SARS-CoV-2 research activities and other relevant multi-national research activities was a critical exercise allowing the COVRIN project to ensure the work undertaken did not overlap with other SARS-CoV-2 research activities.

The COVRIN WP0 team distributed this database to work package leaders and task leaders, recommending them to reach out to the coordinators of these activities, as appropriate, to avoid such overlaps.

Deliverable D0.3.1 “Scoping review of European Union-supported COVID-19 research activities” (<https://zenodo.org/record/5537781>), and the associated database of identified COVID-19 research activities (<https://zenodo.org/record/5533808>).

ST0.3.2 – Organization and evaluation of the kick-off meeting (M40 – M48)

A very successful kick-off meeting was held online (due to the pandemic) in March 2021. A meeting report and work package presentations have been made available to COVRIN participants through the SharePoint and have been uploaded to Zenodo as Deliverable D0.3.2 “Report on the COVRIN kick-off meeting, 31st March 2021.

Deliverable D0.3.2 “Report on the COVRIN kick-off meeting, <https://zenodo.org/record/6010878>

ST0.3.3 – Reporting mid-term (M40 – M57)

A mid-term meeting was held online 27th June 2022. Updates and outputs of all 5 work packages were presented by the work package leaders. Presentations are available on the COVRIN project group site and uploaded on Zenodo.

Deliverable D0.3.3 mid-term meeting combined presentations: <https://zenodo.org/record/7433656>

ST0.3.4 – Reporting project end (M40 – M63)

A final meeting was held near Teramo, Italy on 5-6th December 2022. The aim of the meeting was to discuss progress and outstanding work on tasks and sub-tasks while highlighting dissemination of results in publications, conferences, and communications to stakeholders. Plans were made or outstanding deliverables in each workpackage and plans made to ensure completion before project end (M63).

Deliverable D0.3.4: Project end report: <https://zenodo.org/record/7781538> and presentations : <https://zenodo.org/record/7781504>

WP1 Detection of SARS-CoV-2 in animal reservoirs and hosts, and the environment

JIP06-WP1-T1.1 SARS-CoV2 molecular diagnostics in livestock, wildlife, pets and environment

ST1.1.1, Molecular detection of SARS-CoV2 in companion animals and livestock (M40-63)

ST 1.1.2, Molecular detection of SARS-CoV2 in wildlife (M40-63)

These 2 subtasks and their deliverables have been combined to avoid repetitiveness in the documentation.

At the beginning of the project the WP1 collaborators began by utilising the data from the scoping exercise (WP0) and the SharePoint site to share and harmonise the various molecular diagnostic assays available within the partner institutes.

A record of available specimens from domestic and wildlife animals was initiated at the start of the project revealing that there were initially low numbers of samples available to the participating labs,

and these included domestic animals from households with COVID-19 diagnosed owners. Therefore, surveys and projects were initiated in the participating COVRIN laboratories to get a better overview on the frequencies of such infections.

Activities included initiating compilation and upload of available methods and materials to the COVRIN site, for sharing among partners and contribution to deliverables.

Testing for SARS-CoV-2 by genome detection (with molecular methods) in the participating COVRIN laboratories was the most widely implemented method of detection.

Six molecular assays have been assessed in partner laboratories and shared, including real-time quantitative PCR and nested PCR. In addition, a general CoV probe capture target enrichment assay has been designed and shown to increase the sensitivity of detection by two orders of magnitude over a broad range of input nucleic acids concentrations and a diverse set of different coronaviruses. This assay will be a valuable tool to improve coronavirus surveillance and source attribution.

Deliverable D1.1 “Report on available data from SARS-CoV-2 genome detection in companion animals, livestock and wildlife.” <https://zenodo.org/record/7795565>

ST 1.1.3 Molecular detection of SARS-CoV2 in environmental samples.

This task has been moved to ST1.3 as the information and data are directly relevant to each other.

JIP06-WP1-T1.2 Immunological SARS-CoV-2 diagnostics in domestic and wildlife animals

ST1.2.1 – Evaluation of virus antigen detection in clinical samples from animals (M40 – M63)

Antigen tests detect the viral proteins, often using immunochemistry for rapid application. More than five possible assay protocols were compiled in a database of established diagnostic protocols. A draft proposal for a harmonized protocol for rapid antigen test was established, an interlaboratory trial was developed and undertaken.

Deliverable 1.2.1 “Report on methods for virus antigen detection in clinical samples from animals” <https://zenodo.org/record/7655989>

ST1.2.2 – Evaluation of antibody testing in livestock, companion animals and wildlife (M40 – M63)

Serology indirectly detects current or previous infection through the presence of virus specific antibodies. As with the above test, initially a database of established protocols for antibody detection was set up representing all assays from partner institutes. The serology database included ELISAs (PIWET), double antigen ELISAs (IZSLER), virus neutralisation tests (VNT) (APHA, IZSLER), Pseudotype Virus Neutralization test (APHA).

An interlaboratory test for antibody detection was organised and a panel of 20 sera including positive and negative controls from different animal species was prepared and sent to all partners who intended to participate.

Novel antibodies for use in serological assays and antigen detection tests have also been generated and assessed. These include antibodies against the nucleoprotein (N protein) and spike protein using recombinant proteins expressed in *E. coli* and Baculovirus respectively, and against whole inactivated virus. These monoclonal antibodies (Mabs) are being assessed for their ability to bind different SARS-CoV-2 variants with potential for use in antigen tests (ST 1.2). Finally, the recombinant proteins themselves were assessed for their potential in double-antigen ELISAs which can be used to detect antibodies in any species.

Serological surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 was also conducted in domestic and wildlife animals, using different approaches depending on the risk of infection or exposure to other susceptible

animals of humans.

As an example, in addition to the molecular testing described in T1.1, APHA (P21) has undertaken serological testing on samples collected from wildlife and companion animals. To date a total of 258 wildlife samples have been tested by ELISA and VNT from fox (n=4), deer (n=102), mink (n=1), badger (n=136), stoat (n=11) and squirrel (n=4). Samples from one badger, one fallow deer and one fox were positive by VNT (tested by delta and omicron variants) in two independent tests. Five badger serum samples tested non-negative by SARS-CoV-2 ELISA however these were negative by VNT. A total of 3287 serum samples from the pet travel scheme for rabies were tested for SARS-CoV-2 antibodies. A total of 54/619 cat sera (8.72%) and 208/2668 dog sera (7.80%) samples tested ELISA positive for SARS-CoV-2 antibodies.

Deliverable 1.2.2 “Report on available data from antibody testing in livestock, companion animals and wildlife”. <https://zenodo.org/record/7635513>

JIP06-WP1-T1.3 - Definition of bioavailability of virus in fomites, water and in the environment (M40 – M63)

Subtask 1.1.3 (detection of SARS-CoV-2 in environmental samples) has been moved into this section and its deliverable combined with D1.3 to avoid repetitiveness in the documentation.

ST 1.1.3 Molecular detection of SARS-CoV2 in environmental samples.

This task is important to understand the relevance of detecting virus in the environment, by assessing whether the virus is infectious over time and at different temperatures.

Initially, the contributors met and agreed an approach to achieve this task. These included literature searches to collect infectivity data from other sources than available from partner institutes and data input from research activities of partner institutes collected via an inventory sheet.

The literature search was set up including a form to collect infectivity data from other sources than available from partner institutes, based upon the scoping report from WP0 (deliverable D0.3.1). Data from the research activities of partner institutes was then collected via an inventory sheet and included in D1.3, see link below.

ST1.3.1 - Discuss the relevance of detecting SARS-CoV-2 in fomites and the environment (M40 – M63)

Detection data can provide insight whether and to which extent different environmental routes may play a role in the human-animal transmission of SARS-CoV-2. A graphical scheme was drafted to provide an overview of various potential environmental routes that may play a role in human-animal transmission of SARS-CoV-2. Next to the relevance of detecting SARS-CoV-2 in the environment, challenges faced by environmental sampling of live SARS-CoV-2 have been discussed during project meetings. The definition of bioavailability is not (commonly) used within the field of virology. Therefore, the terms infectivity or viability were suggested as better alternatives and were used in the final deliverable.

ST1.3.2 - Assess infectivity of the virus over time, and at different temperatures (M40 – M63)

At the beginning of the project Infectivity data of live SARS-CoV-2 from environmental sampling (field studies) was limitedly available among partner institutes. Activities of partner institutes that contributed to this area included, for example, persistence in food and packaging, sewage water surveillance (humans), experimental SARS-CoV-2 studies on survival/decay in environmental matrices, SARS-CoV-2 transmission in animal models, environmental sampling at (mink) farms and in aerosols. To obtain information on infectivity of SARS-CoV-2 in environmental sources of

both field and experimental studies, a literature review was conducted. Data from the literature searches and data collection from partner institutes have contributed to deliverable 1.3 (see below).

ST1.3.3 - Comparison with RNA quantification (PCR versus live virus) to inform risk assessments (M40 – M63)

Detection data of live SARS-CoV-2 studies were compared to detection data from PCR studies (obtained in T1.1). This is crucial to inform the risk of SARS-CoV-2 detection in the environment.

Detailed information is provided in deliverable D1.3, but in summary:

- 1) No viral RNA was detected in food, water or swabs of the cage surfaces but was detected at a low level in fur swab samples collected from ferret in vivo studies undertaken at APHA (P21) as described in ST 2.4.3. No infectious virus could be re-isolated.
- 2) SARS-CoV-2 survival on ferret pelts was assessed and showed that infectious virus was detected on fur for up to 48 hours, this was longer than virus survival in virus transport medium incubated at 34°C (mimicking ferret body temperature) which was only up to 24 hours (James et al. 2022).
- 3) Porcine armpit skin was used as a model for human forearm skin to assess survival of SARS-CoV-2 variants. A general trend with all variants (alpha, beta, gamma, delta) were seen where SARS-CoV-2 viral RNA was detected on skin incubated up to 72 hours at 35.2°C, however the amount of viral RNA decreased substantially in the first few hours. This suggests that the amount of infectious virus present on skin after several hours may be relatively low and thus skin may not be a high risk factor as a fomite for virus transmission.
- 4) SARS-CoV-2 contaminated porcine skin was used to ascertain whether skin could initiate infection in ferrets (described in ST 2.4.3). In summary, SARS-CoV-2 virus applied to porcine skin and rubbed on the oro-nasal surfaces of ferrets resulted in robust infection with shedding of viral RNA from oro-nasal routes and infectious virus re-isolated from each ferret. Viral RNA was also detected in air samples collected from within the cages of ferrets intranasally infected with SARS-CoV-2 and in the room. However, the viral load in the air samples were considerably lower than that detected in the nasal washes and throat swabs obtained directly from the animals, thus virus re-isolation from the air filters was not obtained.

Deliverable 1.3 “Report on the bioavailability of virus in fomites, water and the environment and genome detection in environmental samples.” <https://zenodo.org/record/7788426>

WP2: – SARS-CoV-2 characterization

Two main overall operational objectives of COVRIN

1. To identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV2
2. To generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV2

JIP06-WP2-T2.1 – Genome analyses (M40 – M54)

Task 2.1 was focused on the analyses of whole genome sequences of SARS-CoV-2 strains circulating in humans and animals. This approach aimed to promoting protocol sharing/harmonization, and also mapping evolutionary changes of SARS-CoV-2 viruses isolated within and across human and different animal species, as a means to identify mutations and recombination events driving adaptation to alternative hosts.

ST2.1.1 – Protocol repository (M40 – M45)

In order to lay the foundation for the compilation of a comprehensive NGS-related protocol repository for SARS-CoV-2 (and other coronaviruses), two surveys were circulated among COVRIN partners to collect the following information:

- 1) A summary description of the methodologies used for sample preparation for NGS and subsequent data analysis, named “Protocol Repository NGS procedures”.
- 2) An overview of the key steps of the bioinformatics pipeline(s) used for the analysis of SARS-CoV-2 NGS data, named Survey Bioinformatics pipeline.

Deliverable D2.1.1 “Report on the established website protocol repository”.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5342577>

ST2.1.2 – Harmonisation of sampling and methods for NGS (M40 – M50)

A Bioinformatics Ring Trial was carried out to assess the reproducibility of bioinformatics pipelines (i.e., from raw reads to consensus sequences, using reference-based mapping) currently being applied for genome analyses of SARS-CoV-2 (and other coronaviruses - CoV) across the partners institutes.

The exercise mainly focused on assessing whether the bioinformatics pipelines used by COVRIN partners generate concordant consensus sequences from the same raw read data and further identifying critical bioinformatics analysis aspects of reference-based viral genome reconstruction (rather than ranking the performance of pipelines, which were kept fully anonymous). Despite the good congruence in Pango lineage assignment between consensus sequences provided by the different participants, a few critical issues were identified in some pipelines that challenged the comparative analysis and discussion of the results, as discussed in detail in the deliverable:

Deliverable D2.1.2 “Report on the comparison of variants and reference sample exchange”.

<https://zenodo.org/record/6458215>

ST2.1.3 – Development of an algorithm for novel virus assessment (M40 – M54)

ST2.1.3 focused on building bridges between several One Health EJP projects to promote the integration of bioinformatics tools that enable phylogenetic analysis and investigation for virulence traits (e.g., mutations known to play a direct role in receptor binding or antibody recognition) that can aid the identification of drivers for the emergence and spread of new viral threats and the generation of supportive data for risk assessment.

IZSAM (IT) team first developed and published a method for rapid large-scale phylogenetic inferences of SARS-CoV-2 samples, called vcf2mst (<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-021-08112-0>). In the COVRIN ST2.1.3, the tool has been enhanced to:

- i) manage the inclusion/exclusion of genome sub-covered regions;
- ii) accept input from INSA (P36) algn2pheno tool (<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/algn2pheno>), which was developed under “TELE-VIR: Point-of-incidence toolbox for emerging virus threats” project (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-tele-vir/>);
- iii) accept input from Nextclade (<https://clades.nextstrain.org/>) output file format;
- iv) accept input from any CSV file format using a flexible input method;
- v) integrate vcf2mst into INSA (P36) ReporTree tool (<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ReporTree>), which is a flexible pipeline developed in the frame of the One Health EJP project “BeOne: Building Integrative Tools

for One Health Surveillance” (<https://onehealthjrp.eu/jrp-beone/>) that facilitates the detection of genetic clusters and their linkage to epidemiological data for multiple pathogens. This activity reflects the integrative role of COVRIN by building bridges between other ongoing One Health EJP projects and, thus, enhancing our ability to detect and survey human and animal pathogens.

Another important goal of COVRIN ST2.1.3 was to employ genomic tools that can facilitate the selection of strains to be used for downstream biological characterization *in vivo* and *in vitro*. In this context, IZSAM (P28) applied the “align2pheno” tool for the selection of viral strains for *in vivo* work in hACE2-transgenic mice (also related to JIP06-WP2-T2.3 – Development and optimization of animal models (M43 – M60)). For this, SARS-CoV-2 Spike alignments from IZSAM sequence collection were screened using the align2pheno tool against two databases:

- i) “COG-UK Antigenic mutations” (<https://sars2.cvr.gla.ac.uk/cog-uk/>; hosted by the COG-UK consortium), which currently includes >500 Spike amino acid replacements reported to confer antigenic change;
- ii) “Pokay” database (<https://github.com/nodrogluap/pokay>; hosted by University of Calgary, Canada), which is a literature-based compilation of hundreds of SARS-CoV-2 mutations potentially linked to multiple phenotypes. The align2pheno tool allowed the rapid generation of user-friendly reports on repertoire of “relevant” mutations and their potential impact on phenotype, thus facilitating the identification and selection of viruses with potentially distinct phenotypic (e.g. antigenic) profiles for downstream comparative assays.

Of note, this task also covered IZSAM (P28) activities regarding the analysis of the performance of different sequencing protocols to choose the best for downstream activities, with the selected protocol being adopted by IZSAM for routine genomic surveillance of SARS-CoV-2.

Phylogenetic analyses and outbreak investigations conducted with the newly adopted protocol to identify and characterize emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants are also described in the JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN-D.2.1.2 Deliverable (<https://zenodo.org/record/6458215>).

In summary, all activities promoted by COVRIN ST2.1.3 shows the advantage of building bridges between ongoing One Health EJP projects to enhance the identification of drivers for the emergence and spread of new pathogen threats and the generation of supportive data for risk assessment.

Deliverable D2.1.3 “Report on the development of an algorithm for novel virus assessment”.
<https://zenodo.org/record/6784044>

JIP06-WP2-T2.2 - In vitro and ex vivo biological characterization of SARS-CoV-2 (M40 – M57)
Task 2.2 was focused on the assessment of *in vitro* systems for characterization of SARS-CoV-2 strains. *Ex vivo* explants and air-liquid interphase cultures of several animal species were infected with SARS-CoV-2.

ST2.2.1 – Cell culturing (M40 – M48)

List of animal cell lines among partner institutes were collected by NVI (P33) and task was completed in Dec 2021. Various animal cell lines have been tested for SARS-CoV-2 susceptibility. Samples from infection experiments have been exchanged between FLI – P10 and NVI – P33. IZSLER (P29) tested the susceptibility of several cell lines (VERO E6 (IZSLER-BS CL87), VERO (IZSLER-BS CL86), MARC-145 (IZSLER-TCL127), BAT-FIBROBLASTS, TB1LU (IZSLER-BS CL 84) CACO2 (IZSLER-BS TCL 87) and HRT18 (IZSLER-TCL 26)) by inoculating different dilutions of a field strain (SARS-CoV-2 HCoV-19/Italy/310902/46/2020, EPI_ISL_9011947) with known viral

titre and evaluation at 3 and 5 DPI of the cytophage effect (CPE score based on % affected cells) and antigen detection by Mab-based sandwich Elisa. Good susceptibility was observed for Vero E6, Vero and Marc145, as evidenced by CPE and Mab-based sandwich ELISA. Caco-2 cells also showed good susceptibility, as evidenced by the Mab-sandwich ELISA, although no true CPE was observed but only a discrete cellular change compared to the control. No susceptibility was observed for bat cell lines and HRT18 cells. FLI (P10) has tested 28 cell lines of various animal origin. Whereas most cell lines were not susceptible to SARS-CoV-2 infection, some of human, pig, hamster and wild boar origin exhibited limited infection/spread, whereas two cell lines of wild boar origin were highly susceptible and exhibited efficient virus spread in the cell cultures. Cell extracts from SARS-CoV-2 infected cells of high and lower susceptibility have been sent to NVI (P33) for further analysis of host response patterns that facilitate or restrict SARS-CoV-2 infection and spread.

Deliverable D2.2.1 “Report on cell line sensitivities, species and virus growth characteristics”.
<https://zenodo.org/record/6302686>

ST2.2.2 Antigenicity studies (M40 – M51)

ST2.2.2 focused on the development and validation of serological techniques suitable for detecting the presence of SARS-CoV-2 antibodies. Experimental data include tests using sera from domestic animals, wildlife and humans on a series of enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and virus neutralisation test (VNT). A series of serological tests capable of detecting different types of antibodies were evaluated. Cross-reactivity of pre-and post-pandemic human and farm animal sera with alpha- and beta-coronaviruses (CoV) including SARS-CoV-2 were also investigated. Results demonstrate that although SARS-CoV-2 is antigenically distinct, cross-reactivity should be considered when interpreting serological assays and this will vary between ELISA and VNT.

Deliverable D2.2.2 “Report on assessment of VNA techniques and comparison with ELISA reactivity data”. <https://zenodo.org/record/7434267>

ST2.2.3 Complex cultures [M40 – M57]

ST2.2.3 sought to investigate SARS-CoV-2 replication in various complex cell culture systems such as air-liquid interphase (ALI) cultures, ex vivo organ cultures or organoids of several animal species. At FLI, established ALI-cultures from pigs and ferrets, where bronchial epithelia are considered non-susceptible to SARS-CoV-2 infection, were confirmed to be resistant to infection with SARS-CoV-2 B1. To study SARS-CoV-2 infection in animal models with more pronounced SARS-CoV-2 lung infection primary bronchial epithelial cells from hamsters were tested for ALI-cultivation. Whereas ALI cultivation turned out to be inefficient for the hamster model, stone marten ALI-cultures were resistant to infection with various SARS-CoV-2 viruses (B1, human isolated of mink origin, alpha, delta). Complementary, precision lung slice cultures ALI-cultures have been established and used (WBRV and FLI) and lung organoids for SARS-CoV-2 infection are being established at WBRV. WBRV (P31) further established organoid-derived air liquid interface (ALI) cultures of human, cattle, pig, dog, sheep, ferret, rabbit, hamster, goat origin. These works provide complex culture models for downstream analysis of SARS-CoV-2 replication in in-vivo like cell culture models in future and related projects. Whereas SARS-CoV-2 infections in precision lung cut slice (PCLS) cultures from hamster lungs by FLI (P10) exhibited inefficient or no infection, IZSAM (P28) demonstrated that ex vivo lung explants from minks are susceptible to SARS-CoV-2 infection (Valleriani et al., 2022, <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens11101152>) and thus can serve as a complex culture model for SARS-CoV-2 infection.

Deliverable D2.2.3 “Report on complex culture viral characterisation”.
<https://zenodo.org/record/7763360>

JIP06-WP2-T2.3 – Development and optimization of animal models (M43 – M60)

Task 2.3 focused on the development of animal models of SARS-CoV-2 infection, pathology toolbox and biomarkers analysis including virus-host interaction parameters.

ST2.3.1 – Animal model protocols (M43 – M45)

This sub-task sought to collate and share protocols, experimental designs and other methodological factors regarding the in vivo animal models in use amongst COVRIN participants for the study of SARS-CoV-2. Since the optimisation of such models is a very specialised activity this sub-task is crucial in sharing the knowledge and expertise already gained by COVRIN participants to prevent duplication and allow further improvements to meet future research questions. As such, a database collating aspect such as: experimental species utilised; infection route and dose; clinical, virological and serological readouts was created. It was found that whilst hamsters, ferrets and mice can be utilised for therapeutic or vaccine studies, pathogenesis studies use hamsters or ferrets given the similarity in disease profile to human SARS-CoV-2 infection.

Deliverable D2.3.1 “Catalogue of animal models in use, pros and cons, and designed protocol sharing and harmonisation”. <https://zenodo.org/record/6011492>

ST2.3.2 – Pathology toolbox (M43 – M51)

Within ST2.3.2 work developed, optimised and shared reagents and methodologies for pathological analyses amongst the COVRIN participants. These activities have not been solely focussed on viral detection, but also in understanding the localisation of the SARS-CoV-2 receptors within host tissues of different animal species. This work expands upon: <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14232> to assess different host receptors in a wider range of species that will be made available under JIP06-WP2-D2.3.2 “Report on pathology per species and investigative toolboxes” in 2022 and here: doi: [10.1016/j.onehlt.2023.100492](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2023.100492) This work increases our understanding of SARS-CoV-2 pathogenesis in animal species and enables a better evaluation of the potential host range of SARS-CoV-2 in wildlife species and also other species as appropriate. Results generated will be of use to future studies.

Deliverable D2.3.2 “Report on pathology per species and investigative toolboxes”. <https://zenodo.org/record/6259840>

ST2.3.3 Establishment of virus-host interaction parameters (M43-M61)

Work within this sub-task by COVRIN participants: FLI (P10), WBVR (P31), NVI (P33), and APHA (P21) . This work included a collaborative study between FLI (P10) and NVI (P33) using samples from the screening of susceptible cell lines to SARS-COV2 strains performed at FLI (Subtask 2.2.1). Susceptible versus less susceptible cell line from the same host species was infected with two different SARS-COV2 strains. In addition, RNAseq analysis was performed at NVI (P33) to study the combination of viral and host gene expression and other interaction parameters at the transcriptome level. The results will be published in collaboration between FLI and NVI.

Another collaboration was initiated between APHA (P21) and NVI (P33) to study the antiviral responses from ferret in vivo trials with different SARS-COV2 strains performed at APHA. RNAseq analysis from tissue samples will be performed at NVI (P33) and completed as part of ongoing Institute projects.

The deliverable included an overview of the methods used to study host responses to SARS-COV2 infection using in vivo models. The inquiry was sent to partner institutes in COVRIN, and the task was concluded in Feb 2023. The main choice of animal models used among partner institutes was,

Ferret (Anses (P1), FLI (P10), APHA (P21)), Syrian Gold hamster (Anses (P1), FLI (P10), WBVR (P31)), Transgenic hACE2 mice (FLI (P10), WBVR (P31), IZSAM (P28)).

The summary of techniques used to measure host responses was,

1. Serology
 - RBD antibody enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA)
 - Virus neutralization test (VNT)
2. Histopathology
 - Immunohistochemistry (anti-S or anti-NP antibody)
 - In Situ Hybridisation (RNA probes targeting the S gene)
3. Immunology
 - WBC count
 - Cytokines measurement (ELISPOT, Luminex multiplex analysis)
 - Flow cytometry
 - Whole transcriptome analysis (RNAsequencing)
 - Targeted gene expression profiling (NanoString immunopanel, qPCR)

Deliverable D2.3.3 “Report on virus-host interaction parameters across susceptible species”.
<https://zenodo.org/record/7767305>

JIP06-WP2-T2.4 - Analyses of virus traits related to zoonotic transmission (M49 – M63)

Task 2.4 sought to use the outcomes of studies conducted under the first three tasks in WP2, as well as those in other work packages to analyse virus traits focussing on the potential for zoonotic and/or reverse zoonotic transmission, NGS results from virus isolates acquired from animals (i.e. livestock; pets, wildlife or zoo animals), experimental challenge studies and from already documented zoonotic and reverse zoonotic events (e.g. mink-human-mink, others) were used to identify and map regions of interest in the virus genome responsible for these transmission events. Frequent or reoccurring mutations will be analysed in silico and experimentally regarding their ability to change virus traits (i.e., replicon system to assess viral RdRp activity, overall virion stability in different environmental conditions or fusion activity).

ST2.4.1 Variant analyses species jumps (M49-M60)

This subtask is led by ANSES P1 with input from other partners.

Partners have sequenced PCR products from SARS-CoV-2 and pan-Coronavirus positives to determine sequences changes when the viruses switch species.

Virological data (infection in animals and genetic characteristics of found isolates) have been combined with conservation of ACE-2 receptor within mammal families to examine the host-range potential of SARS-CoV-2 and to analyse any viral reasonable specific mutations that occurred in animal hosts. Our results could be useful for investigating the potential of SARS-CoV-2 to infect additional species than those already reported (24 with natural infection, 20 with experimental infection and found to be susceptible and 8 with experimental infection and not found to be susceptible). The large number of animal species susceptible to SARS-CoV-2 infection could lead to spillback events and result in an enzootic establishment with a future reverse spillback to humans.

1,527 complete genomes of SARS-CoV-2 strains collected from animals in 41 countries and available on GISAID (Table 1) were aligned to the SARS CoV-2 reference strain genome (GenBank: MN908947.3, 1798172431). Mutations potentially associated with contamination, recurrent sequencing errors or hypermutability were masked. We found that infections in animals mirror contemporary viral strains circulating in humans; in particular Alpha (PANGO lineage

B.1.1.7) and Delta (PANGO lineage B.1.617.2) VOCs were found in animals well after their report in humans (January 2021 and May 2021, respectively), while Omicron VOC (PANGO lineage B.1.1.529) was found in multiple animal species soon after its emergence in humans. Mink and deer are the only two species showing any evidence of intra-species transmission, although in two different biological landscapes (farm for mink and free-range for deer) and the number of sequences available is significantly higher than for any of the other animal species. In both cases, our analysis identified genetic signatures, scattered in structural and non-structural proteins, that have been acquired by deer- and mink-adapted strains regardless of the infecting lineage or the country. The large clades of SARS-CoV-2 sequences isolated from mink in Europe and in North America during different outbreaks caused by the introduction of different variants or lineages, as well as the cluster from deer in North America, show divergence within each clade, likely to be the first evidence of evolution within the animal population within each clade.

In order to predict potential susceptibility of new animal species to SARS-CoV-2 infection a mapping of the ACE2 receptor conservation has been performed and we found that 19 animal species exhibit very high conservation, 27 high conservation, 56 medium conservation, 47 low conservation, and 99 very low conservation of ACE-2. According to these results, ACE-2 receptor conservation should not be considered as the sole major determinant of animal species susceptibility, but rather as one of the factors that may contribute to susceptibility. Indeed, in our study, ACE-2 receptor conservation is not always associated with infection.

Our findings suggest that it would seem reasonable concentrating and intensifying surveillance efforts in animal species that are closely related to those shown to be susceptible to SARS-CoV-2 infection, especially focusing on certain endangered animal species. We should develop programs that aim at understanding the real extent of infection in wild and domestic animals. This surveillance effort should also be able to identify early spillover events caused by novel variants as well as specific genetic signatures that can be associated with heavily infected animal populations.

APHA (P21) SARS-CoV-2 viruses isolated from humans were used to infect ferrets as an asymptomatic/mild SARS-CoV-2 challenge infection model. The genetic evolution of SARS-CoV-2 human viruses recovered from experimentally infected ferrets were characterised to provide information on virus substitutions involved in host species changes. The in vivo experiments were carried out by APHA (P21) co-funded by Defra, UK and the devolved Scottish and Welsh administrations (grant numbers SE0558 and SE0562) and Health and Safety Executive (National Core Study PROTECT COVID-19). Ferrets were directly inoculated intranasally with SARS-CoV-2/Netherlands/NoordHolland_10159/2021 'Beta variant'. Genetic evolution of the SARS-CoV-2 Beta variant virus obtained from infected ferrets identified seven different amino acid substitutions (James et al. 2022, DOI: 10.1099/jgv.0.001799). In separate experiments ferrets were either directly inoculated intranasally or exposed to porcine skin spiked with either dry or wet SARS-CoV-2/England/21178070901/2021 'Delta variant' B.1.617.2. From both studies, nine amino acid mutations were identified. This included four mutations that have been well documented in previous literature (manuscripts in preparation).

Deliverable D2.4.1 "Collated partner outcomes of virus trait change as a result of species change including cell receptor affinity". <https://zenodo.org/record/7454516>

ST2.4.2 – Identification of antigenic site modifications (M49 – M57)

Report on in silico and antigenic cartography analysis of antigenic site adaptation traits.

Antigenic distances have been estimated for 9775 (Wuhan), Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta, Omicron BA.1 variants using human and animal sera (rabbit).

Deliverable D2.4.2 “Report on in-silico and antigenic cartography analysis of antigenic site adaptation traits”. <https://zenodo.org/record/7434388>

ST2.4.3 In vivo studies virus variants [M49 – M63].

Partners 10 (FLI), 21 (APHA), and 28 (IZSAM) have undertaken in vivo experiments with SARS-CoV-2 variants (alpha, beta gamma, delta, omicron) in hamsters, ferrets and humanised mice respectively, investigating infection parameters, drug efficacy, modes and routes of transmission contact and aerosol, disease pathogenesis, and virus survival on bio-matrix i.e. fur and skin.

As described in ST2.4.1, SARS-CoV-2 viruses were used to infect ferrets with SARS-CoV-2 viruses as an asymptomatic/mild SARS-CoV-2 challenge infection model. Another study investigated skin-to-skin and bioaerosol transmission with the aim to evaluate the ability of SARS-CoV-2 Delta variant to remain infectious on skin, including the effect of multiple skin-skin and skin-type touch transfers and to assess whether skin can act as a viable source for initiating SARS-CoV-2 infection in ferrets. The key findings showed that SARS-CoV-2 variants can persist on skin and be transferred through skin-to-skin contact initiating infection (manuscripts in preparation). Further studies have been undertaken with Delta and Omicron (BA.1.17) variants to investigate longevity and re-infection dynamics and the extent of homologous and heterologous re-infection after five months was assessed. The key findings showed that ferrets infected with Delta variant shed higher viral RNA titers compared to Omicron variant infection. Overall, neutralizing antibodies (NAbs) could be sustained for up to five months in ferrets infected with Delta variant with protective immunity against re-infection with the heterologous Omicron variant (manuscript in preparation). Environmental samples from the in vivo studies including ferret fur, air samples, cage fronts and drinking water bottles have been sampled and has contributed to ST1.3.2.

Deliverable D2.4.3 “Undertake and report on a virus variant in vivo follow-up study”. <https://zenodo.org/record/7794397>

WP3 – SARS-CoV-2 risk assessment and surveillance

JIP06-WP3-T3.1 - Integration of surveillance activities (M40 – M63)

ST3.1.1 – Design format and procedure for surveillance data (M40 – M45)

The format/procedure for sampling/surveillance data on wildlife, food producing animals, pets, and the environment, from partner institutes, suitable to inform risk assessment, was evaluated, Deliverable D3.1.1. The investigation found that surveillance data for SARS-CoV-2 are mostly collected in a non-harmonized way between countries, and between different species and environment sites. We identified four topics to investigate: i) data requirements for the modelling in Task 3.4, ii) description of the current surveillance systems, i.e. the processes that generate surveillance data, iii) data available from EFSA (and ECDC), and at what level of aggregation and detail they are available, and iv) how to integrate different data sources.

Deliverable D3.1.1 “Report on the format and procedure for integration of SARS-CoV-2 surveillance data” <https://zenodo.org/record/6771165>

ST3.1.2 – Collection of surveillance data (M40 – M54)

In Y5, a database was created, with access to data requiring approval by the data holders/contacts for each of the countries; Deliverable D3.1.2 provides a summary of the data collated.

Deliverable D3.1.2 “Database on sampling wildlife, food, production animals, pets and the environment.” <https://zenodo.org/record/7006321>

ST3.1.3 – Identification of additional sources of surveillance data (M40 – M57)

In this task, we focused on collecting and summarizing SARS-CoV-2 prevalence data in dogs and cats from published studies, as these are the most relevant type of studies for the extraction of data and their integration into a common framework that needed to be supplemented, Deliverable D3.1.3. This additional data retrieved was added to (and integrated in) the database using the same protocol from D3.1.1. and shared with T3.4.

A systematic review was conducted on the prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 infection in household dogs and cats. A manuscript has been published: Guo R, Wolff C, Prada JM, Mughini-Gras L. When COVID-19 sits on people's laps: A systematic review of SARS-CoV-2 infection prevalence in household dogs and cats. *One Health*. 2023 Jun;16:100497. doi: [10.1016/j.onehlt.2023.100497](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2023.100497)

Deliverable D3.1.3 “Report on the investigation and possibilities of integration of SARS-CoV-2 surveillance data” <https://zenodo.org/record/7430425>

JIP06-WP3-T3.2 - Mapping of surveillance data (M40 – M63)

ST3.2.1 – Evaluation of current surveillance activities (M40 – M48)

For this task, current surveillance activities being carried out in partner institutes were evaluated. Firstly, outcomes from the scoping of surveillance activities in the UK was collated, followed by a detailed list of institute involvement across the chain of surveillance activities for Spain, Poland, Latvia, Sweden, Belgium, Germany and Norway, Deliverable D3.2.1.

Deliverable D3.2.1 “Review of surveillance activities carried out by member countries” <https://zenodo.org/record/5803075>

ST3.2.2 – Identification of key stakeholders (M40-M63)

Using the database created between T3.1 and T3.2, broad categories of actors and stakeholders that need to be involved in sustainable One Health surveillance activities for SARS-CoV-2 were identified. Extensive engagement of stakeholders and actors has taken place in the UK over the last few years, therefore UK-based project partners have been specifically engaged to describe a “case-study” in this context, and the lessons learned. The UK case study is then compared to Norway which has a centralised national wildlife surveillance platform. Despite these organisation differences, there are many shared experiences when considering setting up surveillance for a novel pathogen such as SARS-CoV-2.

1. Understand the target host species at the beginning of the program, then update as new evidence becomes available.
2. Create information sheets, risk assessments and databases using prior pathogen data as a basis
3. If the country surveillance network is wider than a national government organisation (for example the UK), targeting specific individuals across relevant organisations proved very successful. Contacting via telephone or in person provides the most reliable results.
4. Keep sample collection as straightforward as possible tailored to the individual collecting the samples, providing clear instructions, sampling kits and pre-paid correctly labelled envelopes.

Deliverable D3.2.2 “Report on key stakeholders across member countries and opportunities for alignment of One Health surveillance activities.” <https://zenodo.org/record/7788280>

JIP06-WP3-T3.3 - Risk factors for virus transmission (M40 – M63)

ST3.3.1 – Analyses of transmission in pets (M40 – M54)

The epidemiological survey to analyse the transmission of SARS-Cov-2 in both heavily and normally exposed pets (i.e. healthcare personal households and "normal" households, respectively) was carried out (<https://onehealthjep.eu/groups/covrin/documents/>), Deliverable D3.3.1.

Below is a schematic of the survey design for Deliverable D3.3.1.

Sampling pets and diagnosis of infections with SARS-Cov-2 using PCR-ELISA : Incorporating a more specific ELISA test (ID-VET: DOUBLE ANTIGEN MULTI-SPECIES ELISA) produced new results (increasing the proportion of positive results) in dog samples, Deliverable D3.3.1. The epidemiology investigation also included 70 more dog samples from a research group at the University of Alfonso X in Madrid. These new findings and samples contributed to the analysis in SubTask 3.3.2. A paper has been published on this work: <https://zenodo.org/record/7685683>.

Deliverable D3.3.1 “Report on the epidemiological survey design and clinical data (including anamnesis and lab results).” <https://zenodo.org/record/7674124>

ST3.3.2 – Study of the epidemiology and risk factors in pets (M40 – M63)

An easy tool that allows for the exploration of spatial parameters and SARS-CoV-2 presence in animals was developed: SARS-board is an open-source dashboard application that combines data on a variety of parameters based on scientific studies of risk for SARS-Cov-2 in humans (socioeconomic and climate factors) and displays them on interactive maps that may be used to track the evolution of the epidemic. SARS-board contains 3 tabs, displays, or sections which integrates SARS-CoV-2 outbreak data (WOAH, formerly OIE), temperature data (Climate Data Online) and socioeconomical factors (World Bank Data) and includes options to change the base map in order to explore outbreaks combining with roads, topographic data etc, as well as a timeline to select outbreaks worldwide in pets and other types of animals in a specific time period since 2020. This facilitated the evaluation of risk factors in pets, see <https://www.inia.es/serviciosyrecursos/recursosdocumentales/visor%20de%20SARS-Cov2%20en%20animales/Paginas/Home.aspx>.

A Short-Term Mission (STM) was completed in November 2022, where a post-doctoral researcher spent 12 days at INSA (one of Europe's reference laboratories for metagenomics techniques and

bioinformatics technologies). The aims of this short-term mission were: 1) learning modern metagenomics techniques and bioinformatics tools and 2) collaboration strengthening between INSA and CISA INIA-CSIC. The results of this collaboration was particularly valuable to the applicant regarding this COVRIN project: Within the main goal of the COVRIN project (WP3) integration of the fragmented data from animal and environmental samples collected by partner countries into an aligned One Health surveillance system for SARS-CoV2 was paramount. Metagenomics analysis of SARS-CoV2-positive companion animal samples were assessed to determine the source and timing of infection (shedding light into the epidemiology of this novel virus) and the presence of viral mutations as an adaptation to the novel hosts. A short video summarizing the experience of the short-term mission was presented at the final COVRIN meeting in Teramo, Italy December 2022.

Deliverable D3.3.2 “Report on the epidemiological survey results and risk factor assessment for pet-human SARS-CoV-2 transmission.” <https://zenodo.org/record/7660102>

JIP06-WP3-T3.4 - Models for transmission routes and risk assessment in a One Health perspective (M40 – M63)

ST3.4.1 – Listing of existing models (M40 – M45)

To characterise susceptible animal species and assess their potential role as reservoirs of SARS-CoV-2, a list of relevant parameters was identified and used to develop a “Biological information matrix”. Information regarding these parameters for each identified animal species (e.g. Cats, dogs, minks, laboratory animals, etc) was collected following experimental studies and literature reviews. The parameters found relevant can be summarized in the following categories: (1) Infection and disease (Clinical signs), (2) Virus replication (shedding), (3) Pathology, (4) Immunology, (5) Epidemiology.

The first application of these models was to quantify the parameters relevant for cat-to-cat transmission (Gonzales et al 2021).

Deliverable D3.4.1 “Overview of models and parameters to assess transmission in animals” <https://zenodo.org/record/5541335>

ST3.4.2 – Reviewing transmission parameters (M40 – M54)

Systematic reviews (SR) were carried out to collect data and generate summaries for this biological information matrix. Three SR reviews on this topic have been finished: assessing persistence in pets <https://zenodo.org/record/6818321>, (human-to-dog transmission (Decaro et al. 2021b); and assessing the risk of cat-to-cat transmission of SARS-CoV-2 <https://zenodo.org/record/6818343>.

Deliverable D3.4.2 “Systematic review report and quantification of transmission parameters for different animal species.” <https://zenodo.org/record/7789468>

ST3.4.3 – Listing of susceptible hosts and relative risk (M40 – M60)

Integrating on the work from ST3.4.2, and T3.3, progress on the listing of susceptible hosts and relative risk was completed. We collaborated with EFSA, to write an opinion on SARS-COV-2 in animals. In this opinion, Systematic reviews were done to develop a comprehensive list of susceptible species, based on both experimental and natural infections. In addition, an assessment of the risk some of the most relevant species may play in transmission and maintenance of the virus at the human-animal interface was performed. The EFSA opinion has been published and uploaded to zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/record/7789023>

Deliverable D3.4.3 “List of susceptible hosts and relative risk ranking of susceptibility.”
<https://zenodo.org/record/7789482>

ST3.4.4 – Reviewing of challenge experiments (M40 – M63)

A systematic review (SR) was carried out on challenge experiments in non-human primates and published: <https://zenodo.org/record/7685614>. A second systematic review to assess the infection and transmission dynamics in hamsters and ferrets was also completed and reported as a poster <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7447098>. Similarly, as part of the collaboration with EFSA mentioned in D3.4.3 above our systematic review included challenge experiments data <https://zenodo.org/record/7789023>.

Deliverable D3.4.4 “Report on SR of challenge experiments using different host species.”
<https://zenodo.org/record/7789490>

ST3.4.5 – Description of transmission characteristics in mink (M40 – M63)

Analysis of the spatio-temporal transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in minks (between farm transmission) has been performed and a manuscript prepared, Deliverable D3.4.5. This study identified differences in the between farm transmission dynamics between four different virus genomic clusters, with one cluster in particular showing higher risk of transmission than the other 3 clusters. Some factors associated with transmission included the frequency of between farm contacts and presence of specific mutations at the level of the spike protein, in the virus cluster identified as the most transmissible cluster.

Deliverable D3.4.5 “Report describing the transmission characteristics of the mink outbreaks for the countries where data was available.” <https://zenodo.org/record/7789547>

WP4 - Coronavirus preparedness

JIP06-WP4-T4.1 - Virus-host interactions (M40 – M63)

ST4.1.1– In vivo and in vitro studies of animal coronaviruses (M40 – M63)

ST4.1.2 – In vitro and ex vivo studies of experimental co-infections (M40 – M63)

These 2 subtasks and their deliverables have been combined to avoid repetitiveness in the documentation.

In vivo studies: P1 (ANSES, France)

This study was performed to examine the species barrier of avian coronaviruses (AvCoV) in chickens. It consists of examining the susceptibility of EOPS chickens to infection with the three major AvCoVs: infectious bronchitis virus (IBV), turkey coronavirus (TCoV) and guinea fowl coronavirus (GfCoV).

Each of these three viruses has its natural host in which disease has been observed in the field, chicken for IBV, turkey for TCoV and guinea fowl for GfCoV. The spike (S) proteins of these viruses are highly different and thus it is assumed that this is what gives each virus its host specificity. However, no experimental data are available to date regarding this hypothesis, and furthermore the species barrier of these viruses is unknown. For example could we have asymptomatic infection of certain viruses in certain poultry species?

Four batches of EOPS chickens were used in an experimental trial lasting four weeks. The first batch was inoculated with a neutral substance, and the second third and fourth batch were inoculated with IBV, TCoV and GfCoV respectively. All groups were monitored for clinical signs and weighed for monitoring potential disease. Cloacal and tracheal swabs were collected for monitoring the level of viral genome shedding and bloods were taken for monitoring humoral responses.

Organs were harvested for monitoring viral tissue distribution. Naïve contact subjects were also introduced at certain time points for monitoring virus transmissibility.

Analysis of experimental samples is ongoing but preliminary results show that all three viruses were capable of infecting chickens and that horizontal transmission was observed in all cases. IBV infection was associated with disease and TCoV and GfCoV infection was asymptomatic. TCoV, GfCoV and IBV viruses recovered from infected birds will be submitted for deep sequencing analysis to assess their genetic evolution during the trial. For the first time these results demonstrate that, chickens are susceptible to infection with all three principal AvCoVs which will have a big impact on unraveling the complexity of the genetic evolution of these viruses and in practical terms help improve control measures. Mirror experiments in turkeys and guinea fowl will be performed outside the scope of this project to complete this study.

Deliverable D4.1.1 and D4.1.2 “Reports of *in vivo* and *in vitro* experimentations including co-infections.” <https://zenodo.org/record/7789148>

ST4.1.3 – Virus isolation from wildlife (hedgehogs) (M40 – M63)

Our aim was to optimize a protocol for trying to isolate the Hedgehog Coronavirus from faeces on sensitive cells.

Optimization was achieved using hamster faeces spiked with infectious SARS-CoV-2 virus:

- First to see if we were able to detect and then isolate the virus on sensitive cells from this complex matrix.

- Then to try to improve some steps in the protocol to increase detection sensitivity to be able to isolate the smallest possible amount of detectable SARS-CoV-2 in faeces matrix.

Cytotoxicity effect of the matrix (hamster faeces) was determined by addition of various quantities, on different cell lines. We determined the cell lines with the best sensitivity (i.e. VEROE6 and CALU3) and succeeded to isolate infectious SARS-CoV-2 virus from spiked hamster faeces on these cells. However as they are kidney and lung cells respectively, we will not necessarily succeed to isolate the Hedgehog Coronaviruses on these cells. The sensitivity of these cell lines depending on the quantity of faeces, the quantity of infectious virus used to spike the faeces and the protocol for processing the faeces is being finalized.

In parallel, some tests on Mink faeces, which have different diet to Hamster, and on Hedgehogs faeces (found negative for CoV by molecular biology) spiked with SARS-CoV-2 virus are being finalized. These tests would allow us to get results which will be closer to our final matrix (i.e. Hedgehog faeces) and thus visualize the potential effect of carnivorous/insectivorous animal faeces on sensitive cells.

The last step will be to transpose this optimized protocol on Hedgehog faeces found positive by molecular biology on the most suitable cell lines to try to isolate the Coronavirus.

The isolation of coronaviruses from wildlife samples is a technical challenge but it remains fundamental for the study of these viruses and their potential emergence mechanisms.

Deliverable D4.1.3 “virus isolation from wildlife (eg. hedgehogs).”
<https://zenodo.org/record/7789245>

JIP06-WP4-T4.2 - Drivers of virus emergence (M40 – M63)

ST4.2.1 – Analyse coronavirus phylodynamics at global time and geographical scales (M40 – M49, extended from M42)

To improve the understanding of factors affecting coronavirus genetic diversity and evolution in domestic animals and wildlife, global time and geographical phylodynamics of animal coronaviruses have been studied. This includes samples of minks, bats, dogs and other species.

Phylogenetic relationships between coronaviruses were analysed between animal species, and within one coronavirus species in different breeding facilities or operations.

Deliverable D4.2.1 “Report on relevant sample types and hot spots for coronavirus sampling.” <https://zenodo.org/record/5848638>

ST4.2.2 – Trace relevant virus mutations and recombination (M40 – M51)

An *in vivo* study with TGEV and PEDV was set up in pigs, with 4 weeks old piglets mono (n=3) and co-inoculated (n=10) orally. Faeces were harvested daily from D0 to D10 and organs were harvested on D10 during autopsies (duodenum, ileum, jejunum, colon and lung) for search of recombinant viruses.

Studies on relevant mutations and recombination events in coronavirus isolates to gain insights into genetic variation under “natural” conditions (as compared with ST4.1.1 and ST4.1.2) were performed. Methodology of recombinant search and analyses has been established although will require further optimization (Minion – Nanopore sequencing) outside the scope of this project.

Deliverable D4.2.2 “Report on tracing relevant virus mutations and recombination.” <https://zenodo.org/record/7782269>

ST4.2.3 – Evaluate the impact of ecological factors and interventions (M40 – M63)

Of surveyed SARS-CoV-2 outbreaks the observed genetic changes were being investigated concerning their correlation with ecological factors (species interactions, habitat etc) and human interventions (vaccination, trading of animals), and how such factors may impact coronavirus evolution (evolution rates, composition of recombinants, possible contribution of vaccine viruses). This was done for the mink outbreak in the Netherlands to gain more insight into the role of ecological factors and human interventions. In addition, surveillance activities on other coronaviruses in several animal species were performed and the public health risk of the detected coronaviruses were evaluated.

Deliverable D4.2.3 “Report of analyses of detected variations in Coronavirus sequences related to ecological factors and human interventions.” <https://zenodo.org/record/7792714>

JIP06-WP4-T4.3 - Virus emergence risk modelling (M40 – M63)

Specific animal communities were followed over a predefined period (RT-PCR, NGS) to monitor intra-community CoV genetic variation.

ST4.3.1 – Follow coronavirus contaminations in bats (M40 – M60)

Four partners P21 (APHA, UK), P29 (IZSLER, Italy), P1 (ANSES, France) and (34, PIWET, Poland) have collected bat samples and analysed using PCR and sequencing. The full information is provided in D4.3.1 (link below).

Our findings demonstrate that coronaviruses circulate among the bat population in Europe (in countries that have conducted studies), confirm high host specificity of Betacoronaviruses (BtCoVs), and expand the data on the geographical distribution of coronaviruses. European BtCoVs are highly diverse and comprise two genera, Alpha- and Betacoronavirus, the latter including sarbecoviruses, the SARS-related CoVs that were or are the etiological agents of recent epidemics. Coronaviruses, as zoonotic pathogens with the ability to cross the species barrier, pose a potential risk of virus transmission to animals and humans; however, the spill over mechanism of bat-related CoVs is multifactorial and mostly requires adaptation to replication in a new host.

Deliverable D4.3.1 “Coronavirus sampling, PCR screening, and next generation sequencing in bats.” <https://zenodo.org/record/7664384>

ST4.3.2 – Follow coronavirus contaminations in cats (M40 – M63)

A monthly faecal sampling of cats and kittens under breeding farm conditions was performed to assess the impact of human interventions (link with ST4.2.3). These samples are still under investigations for the assessment of feline coronavirus (FCoV) excretion. In parallel, a serological screening revealed a large diffusion of the FCoV (94.4%) in UK. In France, investigations were conducted on the genetic makers of virulence leading to the development of feline infectious peritonitis. Sequencing results raised the importance of the position 1058 on the spike protein as a determinant of virulence. Regarding, the possible SARS-CoV-2 infection in cats, faecal samples are seldom tested SARS-CoV-2 positive. Also in cats, the SARS-CoV-2 virus seems to be mainly transmitted through the respiratory tract.

Deliverable D4.3.2 “Coronavirus sampling, PCR screening, and next generation sequencing in cats.” <https://zenodo.org/record/7789631>

ST4.3.3 – Coronavirus sampling, PCR screening, and next generation sequencing in wildlife (M40 – M63)

Deliverable D.4.3.3 reports information on coronavirus (CoV) contamination in wildlife by collecting samples from different species, in order to improve our knowledge on the spread of CoVs in wildlife and to predict the potential risk of cross-species interactions and early and reverse zoonotic adaptations. Different groups of wild animals, such as bats, foxes, marmots, deer, rodents, etc. were sampled and tested for CoVs by pan-cov PCR and subsequent sequencing.

Deliverable D4.3.3 “Coronavirus sampling, PCR screening, and next generation sequencing in wildlife.” <https://zenodo.org/record/7794484>

ST4.3.4 – Risk assessment and modelling of animal coronavirus evolution (M40 – M66)

The objective in subtask 4.3.4 was to investigate the application potential of data and research outcomes generated within COVRIN for virus emergence and evolution risk assessments to finally help to improve surveillance and control strategies.

In this subtask, data from COVRIN WPs 1, 2, 3 and 4 were analysed on their potential to be integrated into future risk assessments, e.g. on the question which animal species/conditions offer the highest potential for future virus emergence. This work created:

- i) the definition of a One Health risk assessment framework that can assess risks originating from zoonotic hazards in an integrated One Health approach, and
- ii) an overview on how specific results from the COVRIN project and other publicly available resources could contribute to such a One Health SARS-CoV-2 risk assessment.

This deliverable has a deadline of M66 so a draft deliverable is available and will be updated accordingly.

Deliverable D4.3.4 “Report on established models and risk assessments for viral emergence.” <https://zenodo.org/record/7786373>

3. Project self-assessment

The COVRIN Consortium was formed as a response of the EJP One Health to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. In the view of the EJP-One Health Project Management Team, the EJP consortium was obliged to integrate the research activities of the EJP partners on SARS-CoV-2. Given the fact that there was budget available within the EJP to start another Joint Integrative project (JIP) and the fact that all EJP partners had already started research activities on SARS-CoV-2, and with full support from stakeholders, the need to build the COVRIN JIP became clear. As this was started during the busy time of the pandemic, partners were not always able to immediately find the time for integration activities. However, SARS-CoV-2 research was endorsed in all partners institutes and the need for integrating such research was felt everywhere and probably helped to build a successful consortium.

During the building of the consortium and during the running period of the consortium, the COVRIN management regularly consulted with the OHEJP PMT and the OHEJP stakeholders. This guaranteed that the JIP was built in agreement with expectations and later on also enabled the stakeholders to keep track of the COVRIN activities. It is important to reference one of the primary objectives of the OHEJP program in building and improving relationships within the One Health sector. The COVRIN project has significantly contributed to this objective in building multiple WP collaborations across all the partner institutes involved in the project. While the specific deliverables of COVRIN have been delivered, the scientific community that was established to deliver them persists and will continue to grow in generating future scientific research and operational One Health activities. Additionally, we should also mention here the large number of new tools and methods that were developed within the project Consortium during the lifetime of COVRIN: this was primarily possible thanks to the constant exchange occurring among the many experienced professionals from diverse backgrounds who have been working together.

The COVRIN project managed to deliver all the outputs that were initially proposed. However, some of the activities are still running at March 31st, and will therefore be continued as part of other projects. The final outputs of these will therefore be larger than described in the current reports. As Zenodo uploads can be updated, in the very end all outputs will complete and accessible. This thriving activity right to the end of this important project demonstrates the potential benefit of continuing the reporting period beyond the integrative and scientific activities.

From the beginning of the COVRIN project the coordinators have been open to all potential new partners to join the consortium, which resulted in a large consortium with good participation of EU member states. In the second year of the project partner BIOR was added to the consortium. This went very smoothly and resulted in an even better participation of EU countries in the consortium. The project was organized as a list of integrative research activities all having their own task leader. This worked very well, both for integration as for managing the project. A few of the original project key researchers were replaced by new colleagues. This sometimes affected the operational aspects of the project but this could be solved by WP leaders or the project coordination in all cases.

It is worth highlighting that integrated research activities on SARS-CoV-2 established by COVRIN, are worth to be sustained as a whole, as possible in cooperation with other OHEJP projects. COVRIN developed tools and methods for better coronavirus risk assessment and better emerging coronavirus preparedness thanks to excellent collaborations between partners and the rapid development of SARS-CoV-2 research at the participating institutes. In line with the original project proposal, COVRIN partners made these tools and methods available to the participating institutes

and allowed these institutes to generate and share more data and implement better risk assessments, which can guarantee better coronavirus preparedness in the near future. Hopefully, the OHEJP stakeholders and the OHEJP coordinators can help to sustain the outcomes of the COVRIN project.

4. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2022 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.1.1	Share-point for data exchange of the different work packages	42	42	A SharePoint site was create and used by the partners throughout the project.	2, 5
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.1.2	First management report	51	53	https://zenodo.org/record/7445670	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.1.3	Second management report	63	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7778055	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.2.1	First annual communication report	51	53	https://zenodo.org/record/7448604	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.2.2	Second annual communication report	63	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7778068	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.3.1	Report scoping exercise	45	45	https://zenodo.org/record/5537781 The associated dataset https://zenodo.org/record/5533808	2,5,8
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.3.2	Report Kick-off meeting (presentations)	48	49	https://zenodo.org/record/6010878	8 (report)

JIP06-COVRIN	D0.3.3	Report Mid-term meeting (presentations)	57	55	https://zenodo.org/record/7433656	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.3.4	Report Project end meeting (presentations)	63	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7781538 Slide deck: https://zenodo.org/record/7781504	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D1.1 (D1.1.1 and D1.1.2)	Report on available data from SARS-CoV-2 virus genome testing in companion animals, livestock and wildlife.	60	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7795565 Deliverable 1.1.1 and 1.1.2 combined to avoid repetition in the deliverable reports.	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D1.1.3	Report on the bioavailability of virus on fomites, water and the environment	60	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7674997 Combined with D1.3 to avoid repetition in the deliverable reports.	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D1.2.1	Report on methods for virus antigen detection in clinical samples from animals	60	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7655989	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D1.2.2	Report on available data from antibody testing in livestock, companion animals and wildlife	60	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7635513	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D1.3	Report on the bioavailability of virus on fomites, water and the environment	60	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7788426 Deliverable 1.1.3 combined into this deliverable to avoid repetition in the deliverable reports.	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.1.1	Report on the established website protocol repository	44		https://zenodo.org/record/5342578	2,8
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.1.2	Report on the comparisons of variants and reference sample exchange	52		https://zenodo.org/record/6458215	2,8

JIP06-COVRIN	D2.1.3	Report on the development of an algorithm for novel virus assessment.	54		https://zenodo.org/record/6784044	2,8
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.2.1	Report on cell line sensitivities – species and virus growth characteristics.	48	52	https://zenodo.org/record/6302686	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.2.2	Report on assessment of VNA techniques and comparison with ELISA reactivity data.	51	60	Work completed in M51. Upload delayed due to approvals https://zenodo.org/record/7434267	2,8
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.2.3	Report on complex culture viral characterisation.	57	57	https://zenodo.org/record/7763360	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.3.1	Catalogue of animal models in use, pros and cons, and designed protocol sharing and harmonisation.	45	45	https://zenodo.org/record/6011492	2,8
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.3.2	Report on pathology per species and investigative toolboxes.	51	51	https://zenodo.org/record/6259840	2,8
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.3.3	Report on virus-host interaction parameters across susceptible species.	60	62	https://zenodo.org/record/7767305	2,8
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.4.1	Collated partner outcomes of virus trait change as a result of species change including cell receptor affinity.	54	60	https://zenodo.org/record/7454516	2,8
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.4.2	Report on in silico and antigenic cartography analysis of antigenic site adaptation traits.	57	60	https://zenodo.org/record/7434388	4,5, 8 (network)

JIP06-COVRIN	D2.4.3	Undertake and report on a virus variant in vivo follow-up study.	60	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7794397	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.1.1	Report on the format and procedure for integration of SARS-CoV-2 surveillance data	45	45	https://zenodo.org/record/6771165	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.1.2	Database on sampling on wildlife, food producing animals, pets, and the environment.	54	54	https://zenodo.org/record/7006321	3
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.1.3	Report on the investigation and possibilities of integration.	57	57	https://zenodo.org/record/7430425	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.2.1	Review of surveillance activities carried out by member countries	48	48	https://zenodo.org/record/5803075	4,5
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.2.2	Report on the key stakeholders across member countries and opportunities for a alignment of One Health surveillance activities	63	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7788280	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.3.1	Report on epidemiological survey design and clinical data (including anamnesis and lab results).	54	54	https://zenodo.org/record/7674124	3
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.3.2	Study of the epidemiology and risk factors in pets	60	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7660102	3
COVRIN	D3.4.1	List of existing models and required parameters that need quantification.	45	45	https://zenodo.org/record/5541335	3,4,5

JIP06-COVRIN	D3.4.2	Systematic review report and quantification of transmission parameters for different animal species.	54	54	https://zenodo.org/record/7789468	3,4,8
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.4.3	Listing of susceptible hosts and relative risk	60	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7789482	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.4.4	Report on SR of challenge experiments using different host species	63	54	https://zenodo.org/record/7789490	3,5,8
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.4.5	Report describing the transmission characteristics of the mink outbreaks for the countries where data was available.	51	51	https://zenodo.org/record/7789547	3,5,8
JIP06-COVRIN	D4.1.1	Reports of in vivo and in vitro experimentations	57	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7789148 Deliverable 4.1.1 and 4.1.2 combined to avoid repetition in the deliverable reports.	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D4.1.2	Reports of in vitro and ex vivo experimentations	63	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7789148 Deliverable 4.1.1 and 4.1.2 combined to avoid repetition in the deliverable reports	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D4.1.3	Virus isolation from wildlife (e.g. hedgehogs)	63	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7789245	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D4.2.1	Report on relevant sample types and hot spots for coronavirus sampling.	42	48	https://zenodo.org/record/5848638	2, 8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D.4.2.2	Report on tracing relevant virus mutations and recombination	51	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7782269	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D4.2.3	Report of analyses of detected variations in Coronavirus sequences related to ecological	63	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7792714	8 (report)

		factors and human interventions.				
JIP06-COVRIN	D.4.3.1	Coronavirus sampling, PCR screening, and next generation sequencing in bats	60	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7664384	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D4.3.2	Coronavirus sampling, PCR screening, and next generation sequencing in cats	63	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7789631	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D4.3.3	Coronavirus sampling, PCR screening, and next generation sequencing in wildlife (including hedgehogs and bats)	63	63	https://zenodo.org/record/7794484	8 (report)
JIP06-COVRIN	D4.3.4	Report on established models and risk assessments for viral emergence.	66	66	https://zenodo.org/record/7786373 draft version	8 (report)

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
JIP06-COVRIN	M4.1	In vitro and in vivo experiments performed	54	Yes		
JIP06-COVRIN	M4.2	M4.2 Samples collected under farming and natural conditions	57	Yes		
JIP06-COVRIN	M4.3	Coronavirus evolution under experimental and natural conditions analyzed	63	Yes		
JIP06-COVRIN	M4.4	impact on the capacity to cross the species barrier evaluated and risk modeled	63	No	M66	This cannot be completed until the last deliverable is finalised (M66)

5. Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Hagag, I. T., Weber, S., Sadeghi, B., Groschup, M. H., & Keller, M. (2021). Impact of animal saliva on the performance of rapid antigen tests for detection of SARS-CoV-2 (wildtype and variants B.1.1.7 and B.1.351). <i>Veterinary microbiology</i> , 262, 109243. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2021.109243 Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/7788282	Published	Yes	no	No but a pre-published version is freely accessible on zenodo
Lean, F. Z. X., Núñez, A., Spiro, S., Priestnall, S. L., Vreman, S., Bailey, D., James, J., Wrigglesworth, E., Suarez-Bonnet, A., Conceicao, C., Thakur, N., Byrne, A. M. P., Ackroyd, S., Delahay, R. J., van der Poel, W. H. M., Brown, I. H., Fooks, A. R., & Brookes, S. M. (2022). Differential susceptibility of SARS-CoV-2 in animals: Evidence of ACE2 host receptor distribution in companion animals, livestock and wildlife by immunohistochemical characterisation. <i>Transboundary and emerging diseases</i> , 69(4), 2275–2286. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14232 Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/5795457	Published	Yes		4100 EURO
Newman, J., Thakur, N., Peacock, T. P., Bialy, D., Elrefaey, A. M. E., Bogaardt, C., Horton, D. L., Ho, S., Kankeyan, T., Carr, C., Hoschler, K., Barclay, W. S., Amirthalingam, G., Brown, K. E., Charleston, B., & Bailey, D. (2022). Neutralizing antibody activity against 21 SARS-CoV-2 variants in older adults vaccinated with BNT162b2. <i>Nature microbiology</i> , 7(8), 1180–1188. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41564-022-01163-3 Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/7685201	Published	Yes		9500 Euro

<p>Gonzales, J. L., de Jong, M. C. M., Gerhards, N. M., & Van der Poel, W. H. M. (2021). The SARS-CoV-2 Reproduction Number R_0 in Cats. <i>Viruses</i>, 13(12), 2480. https://doi.org/10.3390/v13122480 Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/6818343</p>	Published	Yes		1578 Euro
<p>Decaro, N., Grassi, A., Lorusso, E., Patterson, E. I., Lorusso, A., Desario, C., Anderson, E. R., Vasinioti, V., Wastika, C. E., Hughes, G. L., Valleriani, F., Colitti, B., Ricci, D., Buonavoglia, D., Rosati, S., Cavaliere, N., Paltrinieri, S., Lauzi, S., Elia, G., & Buonavoglia, C. (2022). Long-term persistence of neutralizing SARS-CoV-2 antibodies in pets. <i>Transboundary and emerging diseases</i>, 69(5), 3073–3076. https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14308 Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/6818321</p>	Published	Yes		4100 Euro
<p>Romito, G., Bertaglia, T., Bertaglia, L., Decaro, N., Uva, A., Rugna, G., Moreno, A., Vincifori, G., Dondi, F., Diana, A., & Cipone, M. (2021). Myocardial Injury Complicated by Systolic Dysfunction in a COVID-19-Positive Dog. <i>Animals : an open access journal from MDPI</i>, 11(12), 3506. https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11123506 Zenodo Link: https://zenodo.org/record/5849858</p>	Published	yes		~1822 Euro (1800 CHF)
<p>Moreno, A., Lelli, D., Trogu, T., Lavazza, A., Barbieri, I., Boniotti, M., Pezzoni, G., Salogni, C., Giovannini, S., Alborali, G., Bellini, S., Boldini, M., Farioli, M., Ruocco, L., Bessi, O., Maroni Ponti, A., Di Bartolo, I., De Sabato, L., Vaccari, G., Belli, G., ... Giorgi, M. (2022). SARS-CoV-2 in a Mink Farm in Italy: Case Description, Molecular and Serological Diagnosis by Comparing Different Tests. <i>Viruses</i>, 14(8), 1738. https://doi.org/10.3390/v14081738 Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/7685657</p>	Published	Yes		2466 Euro
<p>A. Mendez, M.A. Jiménez-Clavero, C. Calvo, E. Pérez-Ramírez, J. Fernández-Pinero, F. Llorente, T. Sainz, P. Aguilera-Sepúlveda, S. Alcolea, L. Escolano, C. Cano,</p>	Published	Yes		USD 2200 (~2075 Euro)

<p>I. Novoa, A. De la Torr I. Iglesias. (2022) SARS-CoV-2 in pets of infected family groups in a severely affected region in Spain, <i>International Journal of Infectious Diseases</i>, Volume 116: S25. ISSN 1201-9712 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2021.12.059 Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/7685683</p>				
<p>Di Pasquale, A., Radomski, N., Mangone, I., Calistri, P., Lorusso, A., & Cammà, C. (2021). SARS-CoV-2 surveillance in Italy through phylogenomic inferences based on Hamming distances derived from pan-SNPs, -MNP and -InDels. <i>BMC genomics</i>, 22(1), 782. https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-021-08112-0 Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5645612</p>	Published	Yes		£1750 (~2000 Euro)
<p>Guo, R., Wolff, C., Prada, J. M., & Mughini-Gras, L. (2023). When COVID-19 sits on people's laps: A systematic review of SARS-CoV-2 infection prevalence in household dogs and cats. <i>One health (Amsterdam, Netherlands)</i>, 16, 100497. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2023.100497 Zenodo link : https://zenodo.org/record/7685761</p>	Published	yes		\$1800 (~1500 EURO)
<p>James, J., Byrne, A. M. P., Goharriz, H., Golding, M., Cuesta, J. M. A., Mollett, B. C., Shipley, R., McElhinney, L., Fooks, A. R., & Brookes, S. M. (2022). Infectious droplet exposure is an inefficient route for SARS-CoV-2 infection in the ferret model. <i>The Journal of general virology</i>, 103(11), 10.1099/jgv.0.001799. https://doi.org/10.1099/jgv.0.001799 https://zenodo.org/record/7789401</p>	Published	yes		Free for open access
<p>Lean, F. Z. X., Priestnall, S. L., Vitores, A. G., Suárez-Bonnet, A., Brookes, S. M., & Núñez, A. (2022). Elevated angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) expression in cats with hypertrophic cardiomyopathy. <i>Research in veterinary science</i>, 152, 564–568. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rvsc.2022.09.024 https://zenodo.org/record/7789521</p>	Published	yes		1750 EURO

<p>EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare (AHAW), Nielsen, S. S., Alvarez, J., Bicout, D. J., Calistri, P., Canali, E., Drewe, J. A., Garin-Bastuji, B., Gonzales Rojas, J. L., Gortázar, C., Herskin, M., Michel, V., Miranda Chueca, M. Á., Padalino, B., Pasquali, P., Roberts, H. C., Spoolder, H., Velarde, A., Viltrop, A., Winckler, C., ... Ståhl, K. (2023). SARS-CoV-2 in animals: susceptibility of animal species, risk for animal and public health, monitoring, prevention and control. EFSA journal. European Food Safety Authority, 21(2), e07822. https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2023.7822 https://zenodo.org/record/7789023</p>	Published	yes		Free for open access
<p>Domańska-Blicharz, K., Orłowska, A., Smreczak, M., Munnink, B. O., Trębas, P., Socha, W., Niemczuk, K., Kawiak-Sadurska, M., Opolska, J., Lisowska, A., Giza, A., Bomba, A., Iwan, E., Koopmans, M., & Rola, J. (2022). SARS-CoV-2 Monitoring on Mink Farms in Poland. Journal of veterinary research, 66(4), 449–458. https://doi.org/10.2478/jvetres-2022-0066 https://zenodo.org/record/7789558</p>	Published	yes		1750 EURO

Additional output

Open access but not peer reviewed paper: Counotte, Michel J., Mariana A. de Souza Santos, Koert L. Stittelaar, Wim H. van der Poel, and Jose L. Gonzales. 2021. "Assessment of the Efficacy of SARS-cov-2 Vaccines in Non-human Primate Studies - a Systematic Review." OSF Preprints. April 23 2021. [doi:10.31219/osf.io/u3fwj](https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/u3fwj). Zenodo link: <https://zenodo.org/record/7685614>

Poster presented at ISVEE 2022. Souza Santos et al. Quantifying Transmission parameters of SARS-CoV-2 in ferrets and hamsters from experimental transmission studies. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7447098>

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

Many deliverables have direct relevance to stakeholders, ranging from the important early task of establishing what work was already underway on Sars-CoV-2 in Europe relevant to funding organisations and authorities (D0.3.1 Report scoping exercise <https://zenodo.org/record/5537781>), through to more detailed technical outputs such as a database on sampling on wildlife, food producing animals, pets, and the environment (D3.1.2 <https://zenodo.org/record/7006321>). Given the urgency and topical nature of the research, many scientific outputs were also of interest to the general public as well as the scientific community. For example, one output on vaccination was picked up by over 12 news outlets with worldwide coverage (Newman et. al. 2022 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41564-022-01163-3>).

As part of Task 3.3, assessing risk factors for pet-human SARS-CoV-2 transmission, a dashboard 'SARS_board' was created which automatically updates through a Python script to download new outbreak data from WOA's website (see <https://gis.inia.es/portal/apps/opsdashboard/index.html#/5d44a9b0d8fc427e836dd266ef1125a6>). This tool supplemented deliverable D3.3.2, and is useful to explore outbreaks in animals. The tool is maintained by INIA. It can be used to associate outbreaks to socioeconomic or climatic factors, and thus might be of interest to Member States (or other countries), as it collates information worldwide.

Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries

COVRIN cooperates with a lot of nationally funded projects in partner countries, and also with international organisations like WHO, FAO, ECDC and EFSA. Links have been established with international research networks and projects like the UK Coronavirus network, the PREZODE network and the ERRAZE project. COVRIN research outputs are reported nationally and internationally. COVRIN has always been open for questions from all funding organizations and national and international stakeholders. All significant results have been reported to the national Ministries and also to ECDC and EFSA as appropriate. Of the second year annual report an executive summary was written which has been send to the EJPOH stakeholders and was made available to the national funders. Preliminary findings have been presented at the EJPOH SSB meetings and the EJPOH stakeholders meetings. In addition outcomes were also presented at external meetings and conferences on emerging diseases (i.e. IMED 2021). The aim is to continue

to make all COVRIN results available for the entire scientific community, primarily through peer reviewed publications, and also to the general public.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

Prompt sharing of testing protocols during the project resulted in partners (many of whom became national reference laboratories for Sars-CoV-2 in animals) implementing those tests, reporting cases in animals both nationally and to WOAHA.

Members of COVRIN have been working closely with EFSA on a report to evaluate the risk of infection across animal species. This report includes different outcomes from COVRIN, in particular from Task 3.4, where a number of systematic reviews were carried out to assess the evidence for susceptibility in mink, transmission among pets, such as dogs and cats, as well as pet-human transmission, challenge experiments on non-human primates and overall maintenance of the virus at the human-animal interface.

6. One Health impact

The COVRIN Integrative Project, was developed at the height of the COVID19 pandemic to meet an urgent need to integrate Sars-CoV2 research, with a particular focus on One Health aspects. There was significant activity across Europe on human health aspects of the pandemic and COVRIN was designed to complement those, adding integration of animal, human and environmental health. During the project there have also been substantial developments in the field, many instigated by COVRIN partners themselves, including new diagnostics, the detection and characterisation of new variants and detection in new hosts. Despite this rapidly changing field, the project has excelled at its two main integrative research objectives through a collaborative approach; to identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV2, and to generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV2.

Key outputs, illustrated with case study examples below, include molecular tests, tests for antibody and antigen and also techniques to assess whether virus detected in the environment poses a threat in WP1. Characterization of Sars-CoV-2 variants and hosts in WP2 has also been of particular interest to national and international stakeholders including WOAHA, EFSA and ECDC. These findings have been implemented in national and international reference laboratory procedures and incorporated into risk modelling in WP3. The impact of this research will therefore be in preparedness research and risk assessments and control research (WP4), with associated societal and policy impact improved risk assessment and improved health risks control.

One Health Impact: Case studies

Case study 1: Impact of test harmonization and protocol database and comparison. One of the first activities initiated was reference laboratories within the partner network to sharing information on detection of Sars-CoV-2 in animals. Tests were in regular use in humans but much was yet to be determined regarding their application in various matrices and samples from animals. An example of the contribution of COVRIN is the assessment of rapid tests (Hagag et al 2021). This timely work crucially showed that rapid tests worked in animals: viral loads under the hypothetical SARS-CoV-2 infectivity threshold were detected by most tests and saliva from various animal species did not affect the tests. But, the partners involved were also able to demonstrate that some of the variants of concern at the time were less well detected with implications for biosecurity and need for follow up testing. These results were disseminated rapidly through the partners and to stakeholders using the regular meetings and website.

Case study 2: Virus characterisation. One of the many virus characterisation activities was a landmark human-animal health collaboration characterising variants of concern using state of the art laboratory and computational techniques demonstrated that immunity wanes significantly over time in older adults (some of the more clinically vulnerable groups but crucially that boosting works, against a broad range of variants. This evidence, first published rapidly as an open access pre-print at the height of the second wave of the pandemic supported policies to encourage uptake of boosters among groups most at risk (Newman et al 2022)

Case study 3: Risk modelling. Early on in the project there had been high profile detections of Sars-CoV-2 in non-human hosts (in particular mink) and yet understanding of the level of surveillance for Sars-CoV-2 in animals was poor, restricting international stakeholders' ability to undertake adequate risk assessment. To meet this concern COVRIN undertook an assessment of animal surveillance, with results demonstrating at least 10 partners undertaking sampling in animals, but methods varied considerably and there were significant species biases, supporting policy to increase surveillance activities.

Case study 4: Preparedness. As part of several COVRIN activities assessing potential routes of emergence and re-emergence a study was undertaken assessing the risk of transmission among cats. This demonstrated that, based on available data, cat to cat transmission is likely; the basic reproductive rate (R0) in cats is over the threshold (>1) for onward transmission (Gonzales JL, et al 2021)

Finally, and most importantly the legacy an impact of COVRIN will continue beyond the length of the project. This is through strengthening with partners such as the International Coronavirus Network <https://uk-icn.co.uk/>, and continued dissemination of results through stakeholder meetings (Scientific Steering Board, Scientific Advisory board) and publications. Moreover, established relationships between partners within the COVRIN project are likely to be continued beyond the running time of the project and can contribute to better emerging zoonoses preparedness in the near future.

7. Future dissemination activities

The partners of the OHEJP COVRIN project will continue to do research on SARS-CoV-2, beyond the COVRIN project, on a number of important topics. As such there will also be further research integration activities and additional outcomes of which updates can be included in the already published deliverables. Therefore, in the months after the end date of the project, COVRIN task leaders will try to update the already published deliverables, uploaded on Zenodo, as much as possible. This will enable COVRIN stakeholders, including EFSA, WHO, WOA and ECDC to access up-to-date information of the COVRIN final deliverables. In the months after the finalization of the COVRIN project the coordinators will liaise with the OHEJP PMT and the OHEJP communication team to communicate the outcomes of the project in a PDF brochure and through social media. As appropriate (F2F or online) meetings with stakeholders can be organised to present the outcomes of the COVRIN project. The coordinators of the COVRIN project will also include COVRIN outcomes in presentations and international meetings and conferences.

Immediate plans for dissemination include the International Conference on Livestock, Companion Animals and Wildlife Coronaviruses May 2023 (UK-ICN) and OHEJP Conference June 2023.

Evaluation final report JIP06-COVRIN

Numerical scores (0 to 5)

- 0= Weak
- 1= Poor
- 2= Good
- 3= Very good
- 4= Excellent
- 5= Outstanding

CRITERION	PROJECT: COVRIN		
	Reviewer 1 - New scientific evaluator	Reviewer 2 - New scientific evaluator	Reviewer 3 - POC representative
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the project directive.	4	2	3
Innovative approach	5	3	3
Quality and efficiency of the implementation	5	3	3
Integration	4	3	3
Sustainability	3	1	2
Impact of the project	5	4	3
TOTAL	26/30	16/30	17/30

Average 19.7

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal

Reviewer 1 – new scientific evaluator

The team has achieved the two main objectives which are: A) to identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV-2, B) to generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV-2. This is a very good achievement as almost all the deliverables were completed within the timeline.

Reviewer 2 – new scientific evaluator

Specific WP dedicated to identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS CoV-2. Also specific WP for risk assessment and surveillance.

In relation to the “Models for transmission routes and risk assessment in a One Health perspective” 3.4, it is not clear why the outcomes focuses on “Overview of models and parameters to assess transmission in animals”. Should there not have been more focus, within this WP, on OH aspects? What about risks for humans? It seems a pity that we only get 3.4.2 on the “human-to-dog-transmission”.

In 3.4.3 they refer to the collaboration with EFSA, but this is a job done by EFSA and should not be counted as a deliverable (while the data exchange is welcome). The other items (3.4.4 and 3.4.5) address non human primate and minks. Again the animal-human interface in this WP could have been explored more in view of identifying risk factors relevant for future risk assessments.

Reviewer 3 – POC representative

The scientists have described the objectives carefully and thoroughly. The methodology and approach do guarantee that the results are in line with the objectives. The results are relevant and follow from the described methodology. The quality of the results is high. The alignment is therefore good.

Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach

Reviewer 1 – new scientific evaluator

There is very high level of scientific excellence and many innovative approaches were successfully used in this project. This resulted in ~14 publications in peer reviewed journals, many of which are leading journals in the field of microbiology and infectious diseases. There were also very active participation in conferences and workshops to share their findings with scientific communities and beyond.

Reviewer 2 – new scientific evaluator

Several innovative techniques (metagenomics, linking domestic and wildlife) applied.

Reviewer 3 – POC representative

It is a thorough, carefully carried out research project. It is scientifically sound, and of high quality. However, I do not think it is beyond the state of the art, although I cannot judge every topic, as some are beyond my expertise. Therefore, I did not tick the box “excellent”; I think it is justified to give a score “very good”. Excellent is in my opinion a bit too enthusiastic. Maybe I do not appreciate the project sufficiently. The approach seems multi-disciplinary, and is the best that can be achieved, but in my opinion a holistic approach, which the call seems to ask is not feasible in research. Sharing data and using data for other WPs is however a good aspect and has been carried out by the scientists. Whether it is complementary is in my opinion not necessary, as long as the methodology is sound, the results are shared, and wherever possible or applicable used in other workpackages.

Quality and efficiency of the implementation

Reviewer 1 – new scientific evaluator

The implementation seems to have gone smoothly and there were excellent collaborations between partners. Through many joint efforts, the in vitro and in vivo characterizations of SARS-CoV-2 are very comprehensive even when handling at high safety contamination is required.

Reviewer 2 – new scientific evaluator

Job done. As an example, the transmission routes were assessed with much (too much?) emphasis on pets.

Reviewer 3 – POC representative

The project management was appropriate. There is not much more to say about this.

Integration

Reviewer 1 – new scientific evaluator

The team was able to integrate a large consortium of scientists with good participation of EU member states. Many team members were involved in other projects on SARS-CoV-2 but were able to integrate their other responsibilities with the current project in an effective manner. Thus, the objectives were achieved smoothly and there was a very high level of scientific output. Integration with other stakeholders also went smoothly and some new project partners were also added at a later part of project as per requirement.

Reviewer 2 – new scientific evaluator

The presence of a coordinating WP helped. Multifactor risk factors considered.

Reviewer 3 – POC representative

The project has contributed to an integrative approach. The scientists did a very good job. They have shared data, contributed to a joint approach for surveillance etc. Sufficient attention has been paid to the One Health aspects. However, whether there is an intention to apply harmonised surveillance strategies is not clear, but in my opinion, this is not up to the scientists to decide, but to authorities as I think this should be tailor-made. The project can certainly be a good example of how scientists and policymakers could work together in case a new zoonosis (or an old one) will emerge.

Sustainability

Reviewer 1 – new scientific evaluator

Some of the testing protocols will continue to be used by some partners who became national reference laboratories for the surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 (and maybe other coronaviruses) in animal. A dashboard 'SARS_board' was also created to assess risk factors for pet-human SARS-CoV-2 transmission and will continue to be maintained after this project. Overall, the scientific community that was established will likely to continue to collaborate in related projects in the near future. New tools and methods that were developed within the project will be useful to the team as well as other scientists in the world. However, future usage may be determined by many other factors as well as numerous stakeholders beyond the current team.

Reviewer 2 – new scientific evaluator

Poor because once the funds run out it is hard to imagine spontaneous continuation of this research activity.

Reviewer 3 – POC representative

Other scientists can use the data, the results and various outcomes of the project. It is very relevant information that has been produced. However, whether it will be used in the near or distant future cannot be said, in my opinion. It depends on many factors, amongst others, the presence of Covid-19, the developments in human populations, in animal populations etc. It cannot be guaranteed by scientists.

Impact of the project

Reviewer 1 – new scientific evaluator

The project links SARS-CoV-2 research with the study of animal infection by coronaviruses and many of their results have high impact on One Health aspects. Their findings led to a better understanding of the multiple factors contributing to virus biology at the human-animal interface and have important implications for risk assessment and pandemic preparedness.

Reviewer 2 – new scientific evaluator

Very relevant (e.g. data already used by EFSA risk assessments).

Reviewer 3 – POC representative

Every contribution to the One Health aspects, and every experience with these ‘integrated’ research projects will be of benefit for the society and to scientists and research in general. It is important that scientist with different expertise, from the animal and human domain, work together, share data en be transparent. This project has contributed to these goals. We can only hope it will not be necessary to do so in the future, but if, this project has been of help and therefore has an appropriate impact.

Report on the OHEJP exercise (SimEx)

1. Summary of the work carried out in the project

Zoonotic foodborne outbreaks continue to occur every year, evidencing the need for the public health (PH), animal health (AH) and food safety (FS) authorities to embrace a One Health (OH) approach. Simulated response exercises are useful for the improvement of crisis management plans, providing an opportunity to test practical methodologies in a controlled environment. The One Health European Joint Programme simulation exercise aimed at practicing the OH capability, capacity and interoperability across the three OH sectors within eleven different European countries. The simulation exercise replicated a national Salmonella outbreak investigation, involving both the food chain and the raw pet feed industry. The scenario includes the use of a tracing tool, which was well received by the participants. Evaluation of the national exercises identified common gaps and strengths in current OH strategies, from which recommendations were produced for any country aiming to improve their OH strategy. The recommendations are aimed to support policy makers achieve a successful and robust OH strategy enabling a rapid, effective response to future zoonotic foodborne outbreaks. Additionally, the need for future OH focused exercises was identified. Therefore a set of recommendations have been provided to assist future development.

2. Background

The One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP) is a co-funded initiative under the EU Research and Innovation programme Horizon 2020. The consortium has the primary goal of promoting international and interinstitutional collaboration by reinforcing the transdisciplinary collaboration of the One Health sectors through education and training in the fields of Foodborne Zoonoses (FBZ), Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) and Emerging Threats (ET). The outcomes from the different Joint Research Projects (JRP) and Joint Integrative Projects (JIP) are integrated back in partner institutes to implement changes that are aligned with the programme's objectives. The OHEJP extends across 22 European countries and has 44 partners, including the Med-Vet-Net-Association.

The OHEJP is structured into seven work packages (WP), and runs between 2018 and 2023. Each of the work packages is designed to address objectives and reach different targets. The OHEJP simulation exercise (OHEJP SimEx), was developed as a part of WP4, Joint Integrative Projects, which aims at developing common work methodologies across the three domains of the OHEJP (FBZ, AMR and ET) through capacity building within the disciplines defined by the Integrative Strategy Matrix (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Illustration of the Integrative Strategy Matrix.

The OHEJP SimEx (WP4 task 4.6) consisted of the development, planning, conduction and evaluation of a foodborne zoonosis outbreak simulation exercise, based on existing methodologies, practises and guidelines, adapted to emphase the One Health approach and to be relevant to all conducting countries. The ambition for the task was to offer a unique opportunity for participating countries to practice intersectoral communication and increase understanding between the PH, AH and FS authorities and actors regarding e.g. diagnostic laboratories, outbreak management, tracing and data sharing.

3. Aim and objectives

The overall aim of the OHEJP SimEx was to bring together and practice the One Health capability, capacity, and interoperability of authorities in PH, AH and FS. This project was developed taking into consideration objectives at OHEJP level, and thus being designed to further increase knowledge and understanding of the One Health perspective, improve communication and data sharing in an outbreak situation and explore the functionality of currently available systems. In addition, participating countries were encouraged to define specific objectives at national level and adapt the scenario accordingly so the most could be gained from the exercise.

To facilitate the delivery of such objectives, as well as helping participating countries to easily identify any shortcomings of their national outbreak preparedness plans, the overall aims were broken down into a series of smaller objectives distributed among the different parts of the exercise.

3.1 Part one: Role and functionality

The objective was to highlight the role and functionality of relevant systems and of each sector in an outbreak investigation. Following this part of the exercise the training audience was expected to have:

improved their knowledge on how and when collaboration takes place at national, regional and local level in the event of a zoonotic outbreak.

a better understanding of their and other actors' roles and responsibilities during a zoonotic outbreak.

gained an increased understanding of currently available early warning systems and when they should be activated.

3.2 Part two: Data sharing

The second part of the exercise was designed to emphasize the importance of data sharing in an outbreak situation. After the conduction of part two of the exercise the training audience would have:

an increased understanding of the benefits of creating harmonized databases and data sharing. identified possible flaws in the cohesiveness of data collection and realized its importance in allowing intersectoral data analyses for the detection of clusters and outbreaks and suggested links with potential sources.

3.3 Part three: Communication

The last part of the exercise was created with the main objective of promoting intersectoral cooperation and communication in an outbreak situation. Following this part of the exercise the training audience would have had the opportunity to:

increase their understanding of the benefits of a One Health perspective during a zoonotic outbreak.

Better understand how to create common main messages and identify different perspectives.

Improve their knowledge of how to use guidelines, tools, and practices available, with focus on those developed within the OHEJP.

4. Organization

4.1 OHEJP SimEx Project Team

The OHEJP SimEx Project Team consisted of an international team (i.e., with representatives from France, Germany, Portugal, Sweden, and United Kingdom) of nine specialists with complementary expertise in the areas of PH, AH and FS and knowledge on simulation exercises. The members of the team were recruited amongst the different OHEJP partner institutes. The team had support from the OHEJP Communication Team throughout the project.

The team was responsible for planning, supporting the national conductions, evaluating the outcome of the national exercises, and dissemination of the outcomes as well as fulfilling the project's deliverables and milestones. The project started in September 2021 and was completed in December 2022. The team was in close contact with all contact points at institute and national level that had announced their interest to participate in the OHEJP SimEx. Each member of the OHEJP SimEx Project Team contributed with scientific and expert knowledge and their time in accordance with the agreed engagement.

4.2 OHEJP SimEx Steering Board and OHEJP SimEx Advisory Board

The OHEJP SimEx Project was governed by the OHEJP SimEx Steering Board consisting of four representatives from the OHEJP Project Management Team (PMT) from four different European countries (Belgium, Denmark, Sweden, and United Kingdom). The OHEJP SimEx Steering Board provided the OHEJP SimEx Project Directive, was responsible for providing advice and making decisions on important matters regarding the OHEJP SimEx throughout the project and approved the policy documents created by the SimEx Project Team.

The OHEJP SimEx Advisory Board consisted of representatives from the OHEJP Programme Managers Committee (PMC), OHEJP Scientific Steering Board (SSB), OHEJP JIP, and representatives from the OHEJP Stakeholders (i.e., ECDC, EFSA, FAO, WOA, WHO and WHO-Euro). The Board was responsible for giving advice and educating the OHEJP SimEx Project Team throughout the project.

4.3 National teams

Each country and institute designated a National Exercise Leader (NEL) and Local Exercise Leaders (LEs). Each national team was composed of a NEL, LELs, Local Evaluators (LEs) and a Training Audience (TA). The role of the LEL was based upon the 'exercise director/controller' role found within the ECDC Simulation Exercise handbook (<https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/simulation-exercise-manual.pdf>).

There was one LEL per sector (i.e., AH, FS and PH), and in most cases one of the LELs had the additional role of NEL. Based on the guides and instructions provided by the OHEJP SimEx Project Team, the NEL was responsible for leading and coordinating their own country's participation together with assistance from the LELs. The LEs were responsible for the national evaluation during and after the conduction. One LE per sector was appointed to observe the conduction and together with the NEL, the LEs were responsible for writing the final national report. The TA was identified and invited by the LEL for each sector. As the scenario was an outbreak of a foodborne zoonosis and focus was on increasing mutual understanding across sectors (i.e., AH, FS and PH), identifying collaboration gaps, and finding new ways to cooperate, the TA consisted of people that normally work in an outbreak related position.

4.3.1 Recruitment of participating countries

All OHEJP partner institutes were invited to participate in the OHEJP SimEx. In addition, the institutes were encouraged to invite other institutes from outside the OHEJP consortium, e.g., to cover up for missing sectors or to better represent the national outbreak management. Participation was on a voluntary basis both for the OHEJP partner institute and the country. The original request and subsequent reminders to participate in the exercise were sent out by email to the following groups within the One Health EJP: SSB members, PMC representatives and Project Leaders. Information and updates regarding the exercise were also presented at all Project Management Team meetings during the Spring 2021. At the SSB meeting in September 2021 the recruited institutes were presented and a request to reply was announced to the remaining institutes. At the POC-PMC meeting in November 2021 the SimEx Project Team announced that 27 partner institutes and four external institutes from 15 countries had signed up for the exercise.

All partner institutes that decided to participate in the OHEJP SimEx selected a contact person who become the link between the institute and the OHEJP SimEx Project Team. The contact person from each institute was then fully involved in the decision-making process about participation.

At the time of the workshop for the NELs and LELs in March 2022 two countries had decided to withdraw due to the Covid-19 pandemic and the increase in cases of Avian Influenza. Another country withdrew due to difficulties to involve all sectors, but still participated in the workshop. Finally, one country withdrew due to changes in leadership, but still decided to participate in the workshop. For more information on the workshop see section 6.1.

At the time of conduction (May to September 2022), eleven countries (Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, and Sweden) had signed up for the OHEJP SimEx.

5. Exercise format

An essential tool within emergency preparedness plans is the conduction of simulation exercises, exposing existing gaps in a controlled environment and assessing the current crisis management strategies without the negative consequences of a real-life emergency. Improvement plans drawn up after such an exercise provides detailed and tangible documentation for each sector and

motivation to deliver the improvements required. The nature and scale of the exercise may vary depending on the aims and objectives, budget, and resource availability, ranging from discussion-based exercises (orientation exercise; table-top exercise) to more complex operation-based exercises (drill; functional or command post exercise; full-scale exercise). Table-top exercises are a common format for simulation exercises, offering the opportunity to be completed in an informal and stress-free environment where the participants are guided by a facilitator and encouraged to engage in a roundtable discussion based on a simulated scenario. A series of scripted injects are given to the participants, presenting the problems that need to be tackled. This type of exercise stimulates the participants' problem-solving capacities and develops the communication strategies required to respond effectively in the event of an actual disease incursion. Although table-top exercises lack the full realism of functional or full-scale exercises, they provide an effective and efficient way to become familiar with procedures and policy. Moreover, this format is not necessarily timebound, therefore allowing the participants to allocate time to focus on the critical elements of the scenario.

5.1 From full scale command post exercise to table-top exercise

According to the original proposal by the OHEJP PMT it was stated that the OHEJP exercise should be “a command post exercise, where the exercise management simulate reality as much as possible, most of the institutes' functions are involved, and it is limited only by the ambition of the country.” It was also stated that the Project Team should have enough time to engage, plan, execute and evaluate the exercise, and that the project needed to start the planning during 2020 in order to be ready for a command post exercise during 2022.

The foundation phase started in 2021 with the recruitment of a Project Leader. The OHEJP SimEx Project Team was allocated and ready to start working in September 2021. Within the initial meetings of the OHEJP SimEx Project Team it became evident that adjustments were required to successfully deliver the task. Within the confinement of the overall OHEJP project there was not enough time left to prepare, execute, and evaluate a full command post exercise.

A full command post exercise is complex, even in its simplest form; when planning and execution is within just one country, only regarding their own prerequisites. A full-scale simulation requires a very detailed scenario, correctly reflecting laws, regulations, procedures, policies, institutes, responsibilities, capabilities, capacities etc. Since the OHEJP SimEx was planned to be conducted in multiple countries with completely different prerequisites, a generic part, with a scenario written in such an unspecific way that each country could have adapted it to its own requirements would be needed. The result would have been 11 similar, yet separate exercises.

The aims and objectives of the project could be achieved using a different exercise format – a table-top exercise. Most institutes have previous experience in completing table-top exercises, and therefore have a better understanding of the exercise requirements and benefits. The change of exercise format was approved by the OHEJP SimEx Steering Board (October 22, 2021), the OHEJP PMT (October 22, 2021), and the OHEJP Programme Owners' Committee/Programme Managers' Committee (November 24, 2021). Counselling in the matter was provided by ECDC and the Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency.

6. Planning of the OHEJP exercise

6.1 Overview

Pre-work and organization of the OHEJP SimEx Project started in January 2021 and the SimEx Project Team was ready to start in September 2021. Prior to the exercise implementation, the

OHEJP SimEx Project Team was responsible for all tasks related to scenario building and exercise organization. Tasks included defining a timeline and identifying problematic areas that needed to be addressed, defining the aims and objectives for the exercise, creating, and developing a challenging scenario that met the project objectives and developing all the necessary documents and materials for the exercise implementation. Further, the OHEJP SimEx exercise was built following the ECDC guidelines on simulation exercises (<https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/simulation-exercise-manual.pdf>).

Exercise planning involved an active role and engagement from each participating country. The first step was assembling national exercise teams, including representatives from PH, AH and FS. Each national team was composed by a NEL, LELs, LEs and a TA. Both the NEL and LEL assumed a crucial role in preparing the exercise implementation at national level, liaising with the OHEJP SimEx Project Team. The NEL and LELs were responsible for selecting a date within a given timeframe and venue for conduction, adapting the scenario and adding national objectives (if deemed necessary) and leading the conduction of the exercise at a national level.

The final step in the project planning was the creation of the evaluation plan and the project deliverables. For the participating countries the evaluation tasks included having one or more LEs present throughout the conduction to observe and take notes; conduct a hot debrief after each part of the conduction and fill out a post conduction survey.

The LEs were invited to take part in a preparatory meeting organized by the OHEJP SimEx Project Team on the 5th of April 2022.

6.2 NEL and LEL Preparatory workshop

As part of the OHEJP SimEx Project planning a preparatory workshop was organized for the NELs and LELs. This initiative was conceived as an opportunity to introduce the participants to the OHEJP SimEx Project and to clarify their role in the implementation of the exercise at national level. The workshop took place from the 21st to the 23rd of March 2022 and covered two main topics: the exercise scenario and the evaluation process. While most of the workshop was organized as an information delivery event, it was also a great opportunity to establish an open channel of communication between the OHEJP SimEx Project Team and the NELs and LELs.

The first day of the workshop was dedicated to the introduction of the One Health approach to simulation exercises and introducing the OHEJP SimEx Project. The second and third days of the workshop were exclusively dedicated to the NELs and LELs, focusing mainly on the conduction procedure, scenario, OHEJP tools, and the responsibilities of NELs and LELs.

Attendees were asked to fill in an evaluation form to assess the workshop's delivery and content. One of the most important points of evaluation was determining the initiative's usefulness in clarifying and preparing the NELs and LELs for their role in the OHEJP SimEx. The survey results showed that 78% of the participants stated feeling either very confident or confident on their duties. All the participants who felt rather unconfident before the workshop (28%) indicated an improved confidence by the end of the workshop. Additionally, the majority of the participants found it either beneficial or very beneficial to go through the different parts of the scenario (100%) and evaluation (94%) with the OHEJP SimEx Project Team.

The detailed information regarding the workshop content can be consulted in the "Report on the OHEJP SimEx Workshop" (<https://zenodo.org/record/6973630#.Y5g7p3bMI2w>).

6.3 Scenario

6.3.1 Overview

The scenario of the OHEJP SimEx (“OHEJP SimEx Scenario”, <https://zenodo.org/record/7843626>) was designed to replicate a Salmonella outbreak at a national level involving both the food chain and the pet feed industry. The scenario covered various stages of a zoonotic foodborne outbreak and included different routes of transmission between humans and companion animals. All the aspects of the scenario were designed to encourage intersectoral communication and information sharing between authorities working within the PH, AH and FS sectors. Similar to a real-life situation, the information in the initial stages of the scenario was scarce and dispersed but as the outbreak progressed, the TA was challenged with a sequence of injects noting a growing number of infections and additional epidemiological and laboratory information. Each inject was designed in a way that triggered discussion and challenged the different sectors to work together showcasing the added value of employing the One Health approach in a zoonotic outbreak situation. The scenario was provided to the NEL and LEL prior to conduction for review and adaptation, and when needed, translated to native language. Even though the overall scenario content was not suitable for major adaption, to prevent losing some of the key stones of this initiative, the participant countries were encouraged to propose any adaptation that they considered would bring the exercise closer to their national situation. All countries were given the freedom to add further institutional or national objectives to the exercise, thus allowing each country to achieve the most out of the OHEJP SimEx.

6.3.2 Pathogen choice

The SimEx Project Team decided to build the scenario using Salmonella Typhimurium as the implicated pathogen. This choice was based on the data from the latest EFSA zoonoses report (<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/publications>) noting a stable (flat) trend in the numbers of reported Salmonella outbreaks in the European Union (EU), accounting for about 20% of all foodborne outbreaks in 2020. In addition, the team identified an opportunity to explore alternative transmission routes other than poultry, where production units are already subjected to strictly regulated control programmes. Egg and egg products are the most common reported sources of Salmonella outbreaks in humans. Other foodstuffs such as meat products are also important sources, which are not so highly regulated or considered when identifying Salmonella sources and routes of infections. Using OHEJP SimEx as an opportunity to explore alternative routes of infection it was decided to include not only the pet feed as a vehicle of transmission but also a less commonly involved food producing animal source such as cattle to spark discussion and enable the participants to explore how they would respond in a situation with a less common source for Salmonella outbreaks.

6.3.3 Structure

The OHEJP SimEx compacted a two month long foodborne outbreak into a two-day exercise due to time and logistic constraints. The OHEJP SimEx was delivered through a sequence of 15 injects divided into three parts which closely align with the objectives in section 3, Aims and objectives: Part one: Who does what? (Role and functionality), Part two: Sharing is caring (Data sharing) and Part three: Let’s work together (Communication). For each of these parts specific objectives were proposed, reflecting the different phases of an outbreak investigation.

6.3.3.1 Part one – Who does what?

The first part of the exercise represented the initial phase of a Salmonella Typhimurium outbreak, covering the first human cases report and genotyping results as well as the initial steps of an epidemiological investigation (i.e., the results from the interviews with the first cases). This part of the exercise focused on providing an opportunity for the different sectors to get familiarized with

the role each one assumes in case of a zoonotic foodborne outbreak. The three injects included in this part were designed with the aim of encouraging discussions around early outbreak signalling and detection mechanisms both at national and international level.

6.3.3.2 Part two – Sharing is caring

In the second part of the scenario the TA was under increasing pressure as the number of confirmed Salmonella Typhimurium infections started to increase and the outbreak begun to spread nationally, with multiple regions within the country reporting outbreak related cases. The focus of discussion moved towards the foodborne nature of the pathogen and to the sharing of data between PH, AH and FS authorities. Part two included six injects which required the TA to work together revealing any existing gaps that hindered a harmonized approach to zoonotic outbreaks. Isolates from animal and food sources were included in the clustering analysis to try and establish a transmission chain.

The added value of having a combined approach to a zoonotic outbreak was highlighted in this part, with the different authorities being compelled to question their data collection practices, thus raising awareness to the importance of data availability and harmonization. The epidemiological investigation deepened with the TA being asked to suggest questions for a rapid risk assessment and to interpret the results of a case-case study. Throughout the second part of the exercise the pressure gradually intensified as the number and severity of cases increased and when the outbreak reached the media, the efforts of the outbreak management team started being questioned by the public.

6.3.3.3 Part three – Let's work together

The last part of the exercise was scheduled for the second day of conduction. By this time the communication office was expected to be included in the exercise. Part three of the exercise started with an outbreak team meeting where the TA was asked to discuss and decide on the main message they wished to convey, identification of the different stakeholders and how to address their needs as well as agreeing on the best communication strategy. The six injects composing this last part of the exercise were designed to challenge the team into creating a common message and raise awareness to the advantages that come from having a good communication plan during an outbreak. Apart from communication, tracing and rapid outbreak assessments were also explored during this part of the scenario. In order to include a practical tracing exercise, the FoodChain-Lab (FCL) Web was integrated into the scenario. This software allows to visualise and analyse complex food supply chain networks during foodborne incidents, allowing the TA to establish possible contamination sources and transmission chains. The tracing exercise granted the TA with the opportunity to work on tracing in the food chain and, by including people who would normally not be involved in this part of an outbreak management, highlighting the advantages of having an intersectoral organisation in the implementation of control measures.

The remaining injects covered a series of investigation and control measures like product sampling and recall. At the end of the exercise the TA was asked to have a final outbreak meeting to identify any gaps in the outbreak management and highlight the role played by the different authorities throughout the different stages of the outbreak. To help the team summarize all the information gathered during the exercise, they were requested to finalize a Rapid Outbreak Assessment.

7. Conduction

The exercise conduction was planned to take place during two full days from the beginning of May to the end of July 2022. One country decided to conduct their exercise in September 2022. Each participating country was given the freedom to choose the dates that best fit the availability of the NELs, LELs, LEs and TA. Conducting the OHEJP SimEx as a physical event facilitated communication and networking between individuals from different sectors, promoting the establishment of tighter interpersonal and professional connections which can be extended to a stronger connection at an institutional level. For the exercise purposes the national teams were advised to arrange the TA at two separate tables (one for the PH authorities and another for the AH and FS authorities) so discussion could take place separately on the first place and move on to a common discussion afterwards. Anyhow, total freedom was given in the organization of conduction so it could be carried out in a way that best represented each national reality. Exercise conduction was adapted by the NELs of each country to better reflect the internal organization of the health-related systems, to represent all relevant authorities and their interinstitutional organization. In addition, some countries decided to invite other institutes/authorities from outside the OHEJP consortium to take part in the exercise. Even though the representation of all relevant sectors was encouraged by the SimEx Project Team, some countries could not fulfil this requirement. While most injects targeted the TA as a whole, some of the preliminary information was directed towards a specific sector. This was not only a more realistic approach but also allowed to assess how information flows between authorities.

During conduction the injects were introduced consecutively by the NEL/LELs, who were responsible for keeping the exercise on track, moderation of debates and facilitation of discussions. Each inject consisted of two parts: one for the NEL/LELs covering the purpose of the inject, the expected outcomes and some follow up questions to be used in case the discussion was not forthcoming or was ending prematurely, and one for the TA with the event explained clearly for them to follow. To give support to the NELs and LELs, two SimEx Project Team members were appointed to each country during the two days of conduction as an easy to reach contact point to help with any problem that fell beyond the scope of the LEL's role.

The LEs performed a hot debrief after each part of the conduction, which gave an opportunity for participants to go over the exercise and discuss their overall opinion, identify any issues, and share their reflections on the initiative. The hot debrief also provided an opportunity for the LE to observe the first-hand opinion of the TA and include all relevant information in the national report on OHEJP SimEx conduction.

8. Evaluation

8.1 Overview

Evaluation is an essential part of an exercise and should be thought out from the beginning and designed according to the aims and objectives of the exercise. The primary role of an exercise evaluation must be to describe what happened and identify what it led to. Considering the OHEJP SimEx's overall objectives focused on identifying strengths and weaknesses regarding data sharing, developing intersectoral communication strategies and increase the mutual understanding on each sector's prerequisites and organisation, the OHEJP SimEx evaluation assessed if these objectives were met while also providing evidence to support the improvement of the participating countries' response to foodborne outbreaks under the One Health approach.

A considerable amount of time was allocated to organization and planning the evaluation process. Each participating institute or sector was asked in advance to appoint a skilled evaluator to overlook

the exercise conduction and work together with the remaining evaluators and the NEL on the final national report. After the selection of the LE, a training session was delivered by the OHEJP SimEx Project Team (5th April 2022) covering the evaluation process, the aims and objectives of the exercise and the role of the LE. Apart from the active evaluation during and after the national conduction, the LEs worked alongside the NEL/ LELs in the preparation of the exercise material. To aid the LEs fulfilling their role, a carefully prepared evaluation handbook (“OHEJP SimEx handbook for evaluators”, <https://zenodo.org/record/7843700>) was provided by the OHEJP SimEx Project Team covering all the injects, the expected outcome and space for notes. These personal notes from the LEs were then integrated into the final national report.

8.1.1 Structure (hot debrief, evaluator’s summary, post exercise survey)

Immediately after the conduction of each part of the scenario, approximately 15 minutes were allocated for a hot debrief. The OHEJP SimEx Project Team had prepared a set of questions for each part of the exercise to help the LE guide the discussion (“OHEJP SimEx handbook for evaluators”, <https://zenodo.org/record/7843700>). Hot debrief meetings are an important part of an exercise evaluation process providing participants with the opportunity to share their thoughts while the experience is still fresh, thus avoiding missing relevant details.

As a second step of evaluation, the LEs were advised to compile a chronological narrative of the discussion focusing on the most relevant decisions considering the exercise objectives and highlight the strengths and weaknesses evidenced during conduction.

Post-conduction, a link to a survey was sent to all participants (i.e., NEL/LELs, LEs and TA) to provide the OHEJP SimEx Project Team with invaluable feedback on their experiences. The survey is found in the “OHEJP SimEx Handbook for Evaluators” (<https://zenodo.org/record/7843700>). Data were collected anonymously using the EU Survey platform, complying with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/welcome>). To guarantee a representative value, a minimum response rate of 80% was aimed for. The majority of questions were posed according to the Likert scale with four different options: strongly disagree, disagree, agree, strongly agree. To facilitate the interpretation of the feedback, these options were reduced into two categories: disagree and agree. Answers were processed in Microsoft Excel and presented as descriptive statistics. The post exercise survey aimed at identifying the lessons learned after the participants had had time to process all information and acquiring feedback at an operational level.

The LEL of each sector was responsible for analyzing their own outcomes which were then combined by the NEL to deliver a national report covering the experiences of the conduction, main lessons learned and recommendations for future improvement. The OHEJP SimEx Project Team provided a template for the national report (“OHEJP SimEx Report template for NEL and LEL”, see appendix I) to ensure a level of consistency in the information provided. Subsequently, the SimEx Project Team analyzed each individual national report in order to identify common problems, major gaps and best practices across the different countries. By sharing a report covering all the acquired information all countries will, hopefully, be able to benefit from this initiative.

9. Results from national conductions

9.1 Summaries from participating countries

Summaries from each participating country were copied (thus no changes in text or layout were made), with permission, from each country's national report on OHEJP SimEx conduction and listed below in alphabetical order of the country that participated. The author(s) of the national reports on OHEJP SimEx conduction were instructed to write the summary as a standalone text. The summary should be 100-200 words in length with a focus on national aims and lessons learned. The national reports on the OHEJP SimEx conduction in themselves will not be made public, but the OHEJP SimEx Project Team have used the results, for dissemination events, and publications, all of which are publicly available.

Belgium

For Belgium, the SimEx on foodborne outbreaks was held on 7 and 8 September 2022 in the headquarters of Sciensano in Brussels. About 35 participants of 5 federal and regional agencies involved in public health and safety of the food chain participated. The objectives were threefold: to gain an in-depth understanding of each agency's role and way of working in order to improve cooperation; to finetune the national plan on foodborne outbreaks which is being finalized, and to build capacity on management of foodborne outbreaks within each agency. The exercise confirmed that many of the more senior participants know each other and work well together during outbreaks. In the Belgian context, an intersectoral (OneHealth) approach is systematically taken because of the integration of human health and food chain safety in two of the main partners involved. However, the exercise allowed for a thorough analysis of the outbreak management process and identify a few points of improvement: in case of a large outbreak, systematically appoint an outbreak management team with a designated lead and technical support for studies (questionnaire, case control studies); informing communication departments early in the outbreak; installing a shared platform for safe information exchange and communication would facilitate cooperation.

Denmark

In Denmark, SimEx conduction took place on May 30-31, 2022. Statens Serum Institut (SSI), the National Food Institute at the Technical University of Denmark (DTU-FOOD) and the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration (DVFA) - all three organisations that participate in the Central Outbreak Management Group (COMG) - participated in the exercise. The Training Audience included representatives of communication teams from each of the three organisations. The national aims were i) to improve the existing collaboration in COMG and increase understanding about roles and responsibilities among the involved organisations, and ii) to strengthen the national communication of foodborne outbreaks to different target groups and stakeholders. SimEx conduction highlighted the unique strengths of the well-functioning COMG. The exercise was excellent for networking, which supported the first national aim. The atmosphere was excellent from the start, and discussions were lively. GDPR challenges in data sharing were among the key timely topics that came up in the discussions. The focus on communication was considered useful, and key outcomes from SimEx in Denmark include more explicit integration of communication aspects to the structure and workflow of COMG.

Estonia

No summary from Estonia.

Finland

The SimEx exercise was conducted in cooperation with the Finnish Food Authority representing the food safety (FS) and animal health (AH) sectors, and the Finnish Institute of Health and Welfare representing the public health (PH) sector. These are the two central authorities in Finland taking care of the management of food-borne outbreaks. During the exercise, experts from these two authorities were asked to join and contact to other relevant parties was only mentioned. The SimEx was conducted

as a remote exercise to simulate the probable real-life food-borne outbreak situation with experts not working in the same office. Thus, the participants had to notify relevant people to join the meeting during the exercise. However, a general notification, including schedule, of the exercise was sent beforehand to relevant people of both authorities to ensure adequate participation. The staff of both institutes involved in the exercise didn't obtain prior information. The first inject was delivered to the PH laboratory, and their epidemiological unit was notified, and experts joined the meeting. The outbreak was quickly recognized and experts from FS were notified after the possible connection to food was decided. These people, who work with foodborne outbreaks, formed the core group of outbreak management group during the exercise. During the exercise experts from several other units who specialized in factors emerging during the progress of the exercise were contacted to join the outbreak management group. These experts were identified and reached easily. The management and investigations proceeded smoothly. The exercise revealed that co-operation between sectors worked well due to the long history of working together between these two institutes. The scenario was realistic and similar cases have also been managed previously. However, resources in all sectors are limited and staff substitutes are lacking. In addition, the exercise showed that there is a need for a data secure shared platform between PH and FS and that the FoodChainLab-tool would need more testing in real-life.

France

The SimEx Project initiated by the "One Health (OH) European Joint Program" consortium was set up to promote the OH approach by carrying out national tabletop simulation exercise for the investigation of food-borne health warnings. The French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety coordinated the exercise in France on 7 and 8 June 2022. All the institutions usually involved in the national health alert management process contributed to the success of the exercise. Participants exchanged on food-borne outbreak situations, focusing on cross-sectoral cooperation (public health, animal health, food safety), communication and information sharing, through a fictional scenario. The choice of Salmonella as the hazard targeted proved to be appropriate to get as close as possible to the real context of the investigations, benefiting from a well-developed French organisation and rich inter-institutional experience. This confirmed that known procedures are already in place and working, with players whose expertise is proven. The whole genome sequencing is a powerful method producing useful data on circulating strains throughout the food chain, but its deployment should be accompanied by training on fields. The FoodChain-Lab software has proven useful in clearly visualizing traceability data, but its usefulness in emergency situations remains questionable. This exercise also achieved an incidental team-building goal in addition to strengthening the collective knowledge of French public players involved in food crisis management.

Italy

The Simex exercise was conducted in Italy in three subgroups, each coordinated by a different OHEJP partner (IZSLER, IZSAM, ISS). The exercise involved a total of 40 trainees recruited among employees of the National Health System (NHS) including experts in public health (N= 16), food safety (N= 25), animal health (N= 4). The scenario was adapted to the Italian context and the general organization of the NHS. All injects were translated in Italian. Original supplementary materials were realised to support participants on the EFSA criteria for evidence assessment in outbreak; characteristics of the food production chain being investigated (kebab); Characterisation methods based on WGS and cgMLST cluster analysis; alert and communication system in EU. All groups agreed on the importance of close intersectoral, interdisciplinary and interinstitutional collaboration for an optimal management of outbreaks and the need of strengthening the capacity building for outbreak management, in peace time. Particular attention was dedicated to the hierarchical functional coordination among actors and sectors involved in outbreak crisis as well as to communication, both internal and external. Post exercise survey revealed that the SIMEX was very well evaluated by participants who acknowledged the importance of regularly running table-top simulation exercises as part of training for One-health outbreak preparedness.

The Netherlands

SIMEX is conducted in the Netherlands from 31 May – 1 June 2022. Eleven participants, with background in epidemiology, microbiology, or food safety, joined both days. The participants were representing institutes NVWA (FS), WFSR (FS), RIVM (PH) and WBVR (AH). During the two days the management of foodborne outbreaks in the Netherlands, including collaboration and data sharing between institutes, was discussed. The institutes mainly responsible for managing foodborne outbreaks are RIVM (human patients) and NVWA (tracking/tracking food products), WBVR currently has a minor role. The discussions were very informative (especially for people from WBVR) and it was concluded that in general foodborne outbreaks are well managed, and collaboration and communication between institutes goes well, thanks to short communication lines. Sharing of data is sometimes difficult given the restrictions to share metadata. The role of WBVR in sharing animal isolates could be more prominent, which might in future result in a database including human, food and animal based WGS data enabling to find clusters between different reservoirs.

Norway

The overall experience of the exercise conduction was positive, the participants were engaged throughout the scenario and discussions during the hot debriefs were constructive and fruitful.

The aim of SimEx was to increase understanding of the benefits of a OH perspective, and to identify gaps and needs among and between organisations. The conduction confirmed a well-functioning outbreak response to zoonoses and good communication between the public health, animal health and food safety sectors. Roles and responsibilities were highlighted, new ideas shared and collaboration between the sectors strengthened. Capacity building for the junior staff participating was an added value.

The exercise identified lessons learned to further improve the OH approach:

There is a need for stronger data sharing capacities between the key OH stakeholders to deal with delay in data sharing. Technical solutions should be established, some are already under discussion and development.

Identifications of lessons learned from past outbreaks would ensure continuity of strengthening the OH system. Regular multi-sectoral meetings to evaluate the response to recent outbreaks and to find areas for improvement are recommended.

Food Chain Lab could potentially enhance outbreak response and trainings for relevant stakeholders are already planned.

Poland

SimEx simulation exercise was held on 26-27 May 2022 in a remote format. It was attended by a total of 13 people from two units (National Veterinary Research Institute, Pulawy and General Veterinary Inspectorate, Warsaw). These people represented 2 of the 3 needed sectors: Animal Health and Food Safety of animal origin. Unfortunately, due to the lack of participation in OHEJP of a representative of the Public Health sector, the exercise lacked such individuals. Participants in the Animal Health/Food Safety sector were well aware of their roles and responsibilities in investigating the source of Salmonella contamination. They are also well aware of the legal considerations for controlling Salmonella infections in animals. The SimEx scenario focused mainly on public health activities, in our view little reflecting what is happening in countries with high salmonellosis prevalence in sectors other than cattle and low beef cattle production. Opportunities to change the scenario would not have improved the overall perception of the exercise. In order to adapt the obtained scenario to Polish conditions it would require too many changes and the involvement of people from many fields, which was not possible at that time.

Portugal

The SimEx conduction in Portugal took place between 21st and 23rd of June 2022, at a conference room of the National Institute of Agricultural and Veterinary Research (INIAV), Oeiras. The conduction was carried out in person with the training audience being organized around a table to help facilitate discussion. During the SimEx, the feedback from the training audience was positive, having mentioned that the scenario was relevant and fitted the exercise purpose and objectives. This discussion helped to raise issues in the way the different institutions/sectors communicate and provided an opportunity for

people to clarify how they normally approach a situation like this, which seemed unclear from the point of view of other sectors. The training audience agreed on the areas that need improvement, namely the lack of inter-sectoral communication practices, common databases, and guidelines for coordination in cases of an outbreak.

Sweden

On June 14-15 2022, the SimEx exercise was held in Uppsala, Sweden, at the Swedish Food Agency (SLV) with participants from the SLV, the National Veterinary Institute (SVA), the Swedish Board of Agriculture (SJV) and the Public Health Agency of Sweden (Fohm). The exercise aimed at improving the participants' knowledge and understanding regarding the roles and responsibilities of different authorities, how collaboration occurs during an outbreak with a zoonotic disease, and how different authorities work with an outbreak. In addition, the exercise aimed to increase the understanding of the benefits with a One Health approach during outbreak investigations, and of creating a common situational picture to facilitate communication between and from the different sectors. The exercise gave ample time for networking, thus facilitating future collaboration. Furthermore, the exercise enabled the sharing of information about tools and guidelines as well as platforms for collaboration used by the different authorities. A major outcome from the exercise was the realisation that personal contacts are very important in the initial phases of an outbreak, which both entails a close collaboration but can also mean a vulnerability when key people for the contacts are absent.

9.2 Compiled results from all participating countries

In total, 255 participants in 11 countries (Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Italy, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Sweden, the Netherlands) completed the OHEJP SimEx. Of these, 205 answered the post-conduction survey. Four countries achieved the desired 80% response rate, and all countries had response rates above 60%. The overall response rate was 80% (n=205), confirming that the results can be considered representative.

All results from the post-conduction survey are available in the OHEJP SimEx scientific publication (<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1121522> and <https://zenodo.org/record/8093285>).

10. Discussion and recommendations

Regardless of the topic and scope, a successful outbreak exercise requires detailed planning and organization. This begins with recruiting a team and setting up detailed aims and objectives. Thereafter, creating a realistic scenario and planning the conduction are important steps. The length and complexity of these stages depends on the nature and scale of the exercise. Considering the OHEJP SimEx was primarily a discussion-based exercise, the major challenge was to meet the expected needs of eleven countries that had different prerequisites. The scenario had to be generic enough for the exercise to be relevant to each country's response framework and organisational structure yet detailed enough to be realistic and capable of resulting in relevant discussions.

The One Health EJP is composed of public institutes in the AH, PH and FS sectors and therefore has close collaboration with national and international stakeholders, including those represented in the OHEJP SimEx Advisory Board. This collaboration has enabled sharing the experiences from OHEJP SimEx to policy makers, whose support is essential for establishing and strengthening the structures needed to implement a OH approach to investigation and management of outbreaks. For the successful implementation of the actions identified they need to be assessed taking into consideration each national reality and adapted accordingly. There are several tools and resources available to support decision makers in making the transition to better OH structures and support them in drawing national action plans that can address the major gaps.

The complete discussion and recommendations on the OHEJP SimEx are described in the OHEJP SimEx scientific publication: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1121522> (<https://zenodo.org/record/8093285>).

11. Conclusions

The OHEJP SimEx was a successful multi-country national simulation exercise. The results revealed the need for initiatives that can support countries in the practical implementation of One Health. With the continual risk of zoonotic foodborne outbreaks there is a need to invest in prevention and contingency, as well as building capacity to respond to a health emergency, using a OH approach.

Future OH simulation exercises can build on the OHEJP SimEx structure and experiences and should try to address the identified limitations. All participants acknowledged the essential tasks to engage with stakeholders and policy makers in order to ensure the framework of practical implementation of a OH approach is supported.

12. Deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

Project deliverable number	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>
D4.30	Report on the OHEJP exercise (SimEx) - planning, conduction and evaluation	M63	M63 (short version) M66 (full version)	Public The full version was confidential until the scientific article was published. https://zenodo.org/record/7843557

Milestones

Milestone name	Delivery date	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
Set date and venue for Workshop	M48	Yes		
Assigned LEL and NEL	M48	Yes		
Questions for Hot Debrief ready	M50	Yes		
SimEx Workshop	M51	Yes		

Digital Evaluation Instruction ready for Local Evaluators	M52	Yes		
National Report Template Ready	M53	Yes		
All exercises conducted	M56	No	M57	One country asked to conduct the exercise in M57.
Reports submitted to OHEJP exercise team	M57	No	M58	One country submitted the national report in M58.

13. Publications and other output

Publications

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>A multi-country One Health foodborne outbreak simulation exercise: cross-sectoral cooperation, data sharing and communication.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1121522 https://zenodo.org/record/8093285</p>	Yes		Yes 3200 €

Additional output

- “Harnessing the benefits of a One Health approach in foodborne outbreaks”, poster OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022 <https://zenodo.org/record/6463306>
- Report on the OHEJP SimEx Workshop <https://zenodo.org/record/6973630#.Y2y6Y3bMI2w>
- One Health EJP Report on the Joint SimEx/Dissemination Workshop (with WP5 – Science to Policy) <https://zenodo.org/record/7660178>

Evaluation report OHEJP exercise (SimEx)

Numerical scores (0 to 5)

- 0= Weak
- 1= Poor
- 2= Good
- 3= Very good
- 4= Excellent
- 5= Outstanding

CRITERION	PROJECT: SimEx		
	Reviewer 1 - New scientific evaluator	Reviewer 2 - New scientific evaluator	Reviewer 3 - POC representative
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the project directive.	5	4	4
Innovative approach	4	4	2
Quality and efficiency of the implementation	5	5	3
Integration	4	4	2
Sustainability	4	4	3
Impact of the project	4	5	3
TOTAL	26/30	26/30	17/30

Average: 23.0

Comment from reviewer 3 (POC representative): Total score 17 – This score is not to be taken into account as such since I cannot fully appreciate the integration, sustainability and impact components of the project based on the results of this workpackage.

Since I have to rank I will say that these 3 element are between good and very good based on the fact that the work performed in this WP if well exploited shall certainly contribute to the sustainability and impact component of the project.

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the Project Directive

Reviewer 1 – new scientific evaluator

The outcomes of the simulation exercise (SimEx) met very satisfactorily the project's initial objectives. Overall, the completion of the exercise either confirmed the good performance of the response to zoonosis outbreaks or, otherwise, highlighted the need for improvements. First, SimEx provided a better understanding of the need to strengthen capacities and harmonize data sharing approaches among key health stakeholders, as well as to overcome legal constraints to the implementation of data collection across sectors. Second, the exercise contributed to improved understanding of communication needs and identification of target audiences, according to more than 90% of participants. As a result, interpersonal relationships between professionals from all sectors were strengthened. Finally, it emphasized the role and functionality of currently

available systems, raising awareness of warning systems and emergency action plans at both national and European Union(EU) levels.

Reviewer 2 – new scientific evaluator

Although according to the original proposal by the OHEJP PMT it was stated that the OHEJP exercise should be “a command post exercise”, a complex operation-based exercises, adjustments were made by the project team due to late start of the actual project implementation. As “not enough time left to prepare, execute, and evaluate a full command post exercise. It was opted to develop and conduct Table-top exercises in the diverse countries instead. The project developed a generic part, with a scenario written in such an unspecific way that each country could adapted it to its own requirements and several of the exercises were translated and conducted in the national language. A total of 11 similar, yet separate exercises were developed and implemented successfully and fully compliant with bringing together and practice the One Health capability, capacity, and interoperability of authorities in PH, AH and FS.

Reviewer 3 – POC representative

The results are well aligned with the project objectives.

The project team has well described the objectives, the rationale for the methodology used to perform the simulation exercise to improve crisis management plans, as well as the results. The latest are well described globally for the project as well as the individual level (by country). The participation of different partners in the exercise is of good level. The conclusions drawn are clear and shall be useful to improve (adapt) national and collaborative strategies and action plans.

Innovative approach

Reviewer 1 – new scientific evaluator

The exercise successfully created a scenario that encompassed several stages of a foodborne zoonotic outbreak and explored less common alternative routes of transmission between humans and companion animals. This approach challenged authorities from different sectors to communicate and work together, creating an opportunity to better achieve a One Health perspective. In addition, the exercise included data visualization tools such as the Food Chain Laboratory (FCL), which can be of added value, revealing the need for training and better adaptability to future One Health approaches.

Participating countries were encouraged to adapt the scenario to their own situation and needs before undertaking the exercise. Yet, fluctuations in the Salmonella situation, response frameworks, and organizational structures among them made the scenario more compatible with the current systems and situation in some countries than in others. Despite this, the exercise resulted in relevant intersectoral work and discussions, which can be regarded as a major success.

Reviewer 2 – new scientific evaluator

The definition for innovative in the guidance document was given as “sound and successful project delivery, complementary between the consortium partners”, this was fully met. There were clear roles and responsibilities given to the various partakers of the project and also the feedback of the countries was very positive.

Nevertheless, I would like to use this opportunity to provide some thoughts on the actual simulation exercise format developed. The simulation exercises conducted included a practical tracing exercise. The FoodChain-Lab (FCL) Web was integrated into the scenario. Possibly other additional practical exercises could be further explored as the simulation exercise developed appear to follow mainly the outline for exercises developed by ECDC. Innovations as the use of small clips as injects or the organization of a press conference to simulate risk communication could be considered in the future. The set up of the exercise in one big room with either one or two tables could be changed as to have participants move between tables (sectors) or located in different parts of the building requiring them to communicate through various media, actually more simulating

real life situations. The use of large maps in the middle of the room have also proven to be very conducive to stimulate discussion among the various participants.

Reviewer 3 – POC representative

The approach taken was based on already existing knowledge and practices, which appears relevant for such exercise. The innovation in this aspect is rather limited but this situation appears inherent to the situation and project goal. It would have been interesting to propose simulation exercises in different domains.

For example for an airborne transmission - where challenges and impact might be more difficult to handle - in addition to the foodborne infection example used in the exercise.

Or to try to extrapolate on the exercise made in a foodborne system for other types of transmission.

Quality and efficiency of the implementation

Reviewer 1 – new scientific evaluator

The project management was appropriate, following detailed planning and organization, which are key to achieve a successful outbreak exercise. There was enough time dedicated to prework and organization of the exercise by the appointed Project Team. Moreover, the preparatory workshop helped national and local exercise leaders to familiarize with their roles in the implementation of the exercise, with 78% of participants stating feeling very confident or confident with their duties. Another important aspect to highlight is the significant amount of time allocated to the organization and planning of the evaluation process, which is key to reviewing the objectives and achievements during and after the exercise.

Lastly, a solid communication strategy was successfully implemented within the project. Several outputs were produced, including a publication and the preparation of various reports and seminars that will be key to disseminating the results of the exercise.

Reviewer 2 – new scientific evaluator

From the report it appears that the simulation exercises were very well organized and the different roles and responsibilities of organizers, evaluators and players well defined and communicated. Also the feedback from countries was very positive and therefore the project has successfully developed and implemented the simulation exercises.

Reviewer 3 – POC representative

The quality and efficiency of the implementation appears quite good with a good description of the process, the methodology, the results and conclusion, as well as a good contribution of most partners of the project.

Integration

Reviewer 1 – new scientific evaluator

A balanced representation and sufficient involvement of the three sectors within the countries has been demonstrated, except for one country in which only two sectors participated. This good integration across sectors will hopefully enable participant partner organizations to further improve alignment to support their tasks during outbreak responses.

Of particular note is the secondary role that communication teams played during the main part of the SimEx, as reported by participants from some countries. To increase overall participation and engagement, the incorporation of specific tasks or the inclusion of communication experts in the exercise planning team has been discussed and should be considered.

Reviewer 2 – new scientific evaluator

The public health, animal health and food safety sectors were well integrated in the simulation exercises. One could consider that possibly also other sectors could have been integrated or acknowledged when dealing with a foodborne Salmonella outbreak. The role of private sector as well as quality control agencies and eventually wider agriculture sector, consumers, and others could have been considered when developing the exercises.

Reviewer 3 – POC representative

Integration can hardly be appreciated based on the analysis of this WP 4 only.

Components that are clearly represented and contributed are Public Health, Animal Health, and Food Safety.

It is unclear if the contribution of environmental representatives were included or envisaged in the exercise and in the project, as well as how they could have contributed to improve the exercise and results knowing the perimeter addressed.

It would have been interesting also to explore how to engage with industry or industry associations in this regards to see how to best engage with them when/if relevant.

Sustainability

Reviewer 1 – new scientific evaluator

The exercise successfully helped to identify and agree on areas and challenges in need of improvement. Overall, more than 90% of the participants stated feeling encouraged to adopt the One Health approach by collaborating more closely with other sectors in future outbreak situations. Additionally, some countries already have plans under discussion and development, which indicates the possibility of sustaining the objectives achieved by the project. A potential compromise to this continuity, however, could be the lack of effective and formal structural communication channels to ensure interinstitutional communication networks.

Reviewer 2 – new scientific evaluator

It appears that this has been a one off simulation exercise conducted in each of the 11 countries under this project. The development of a clear outline and guide on how to develop and conduct exercises could have been an important product that could enable countries to also conduct their own exercises after the end of the project. Also the persons trained during the development and implementation of the exercise could be followed up and included into a network of exercise facilitators, evaluators and/or exercise developers to ensure continuity of this kind of work at national and European level,

Reviewer 3 – POC representative

The sustainability of the project is had to appreciate based on the analysis of this WP only.

If well exploited and translated, the results of this project - in particular through the simulation exercise and the conclusion observed - should allow building stronger strategies and action plans in crisis

management. It would be important to see how the consortium partners can keep interacting / further working together to contribute to this sustainability component.

Impact of the project

Reviewer 1 – new scientific evaluator

Overall, the project successfully emphasized the need to invest in prevention, contingency and capacity building with initiatives that can support countries in the practical implementation of One Health, which will undoubtedly have an impact on future simulation exercises. The great success achieved in terms of strengthening networks has been proven, which is likely to ensure a positive secondary effect by improving communication and cooperation between the different authorities and sectors. Indeed, the exercise, while demonstrating a greater understanding of what to expect from each sector, also highlighted the existence of gaps between them and the importance of bridging them. These findings will hopefully be considered for future actions, such as recognizing the key role of National Reference Laboratories and the benefits of including them in training initiatives.

Ultimately, to achieve an impact on the implementation of the results obtained with this project, the publication of Alves *et al.* 2023 (submitted in December 2022) will be crucial as it will contain a summary of the recommendations drawn from the exercise, which will allow reaching a wider target audience. In this regard, it is expected that the main results obtained from the exercise will be applied, with repercussions at both national and international levels.

Reviewer 2 – new scientific evaluator

The impact of this project is certainly outstanding as it has reached the goals it has set out. The project outcomes will very likely have positive secondary effects especially on collaboration and communication between the sectors such as public health/ animal health/ food safety in countries that participated in this project.

Reviewer 3 – POC representative

For the same reasons as above, the project's impact is hard to appreciate based on the analysis of this WP only. Again, if well exploited and translated, the results of this project - in particular through the simulation exercise and the conclusion observed - should allow building stronger strategies and action plans in crisis management. It would be important to see how the consortium partners can keep interacting / further working together to contribute to achieve this goal.

Appendix I: Evaluation of the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP) simulation exercise (SimEx) – An in-depth analysis on actions taken and lessons learned

1. Introduction

The One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP) simulation exercise (SimEx) was launched to assess and improve the collaboration between public health, animal health, and food safety sectors in participating countries to advance their One Health approach. In 2022, OHEJP SimEx conducted a foodborne outbreak table-top exercise scenario across 11 European countries, with the aim to encourage intersectoral cooperation and demonstrate the added value of employing the One Health approach in an outbreak situation, while highlighting areas for further development.

Individual interviews were conducted to assess the impact and actions taken after the completion of the SimEx. This evaluation aimed to gain a deeper understanding on lessons learned and experiences gained at countries with different models of intersectoral collaboration.

2. Methodology

Background documentation on the planning, development, and execution of the SimEx was revised. This documentation was available from the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) and the One Health EJP SimEx coordination team, which provided the relevant parts of the evaluation survey conducted after the exercise. Moreover, the SimEx dissemination workshop presentation and related documents were made available to conduct the analysis presented here.

For the interviews, special interest was given to countries where all three sectors (i.e., public health, animal health, and food safety) were represented during the exercise, while aiming for geographical representation. Based on this, local and national exercise leaders from five countries were contacted. In total, 12 representatives from four countries participated in the online interviews.

After agreeing on a specific date for the interview, participants were provided with a questionnaire to help them prepare in advance. In addition, an informed consent form about the procedure was distributed and accepted by each participant in written form prior to commencement of the interview.

The semi-structured interviews were conducted online and scheduled to last one hour. They aimed to collect information related to the following four main areas – (1) the perception of the different sectors on the simulation exercise, (2) the need for a coordinated action plan, (3) the implementation and actions taken by each sector and/or country, and (4) lessons learned and future perspectives. Some quotations extracted from the interviews are presented in boxes throughout and referred to in the text.

The interviews were planned, conducted, and analysed by Ana Cristina González Pérez, currently working at the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) as a fellow of the ECDC programme, under the Public Health Microbiology (EUPHEM) track.

3. Perspectives from the different sectors involved in the SimEx

To gain a better understanding of the perception of the different sectors on the SimEx, the results of the evaluation survey conducted after the exercise were analysed by sector. In general, the participants were in agreement with the scenario chosen for this simulation. Of note, the animal health sector was less in agreement than the other sectors (i.e., food safety and public health) on

whether the scenario was realistic (74% vs. 85% and 88%, respectively) and relevant (87% vs. 96% and 99%, respectively). Similarly, participants from the animal health sector expressed less agreement about the scenario covering all the sectors involved (72% compared to more than 90% in the other two sectors).

Similar views were expressed during the online interviews, in which there was a common perception among animal health representatives that this sector played a minor role during the exercise (see 1 – 3). Despite this, they seemed satisfied overall with the scenario and the way in which the exercise was approached by including different actors.

(1) “The centre of the question in these scenarios is whether the animal product is safe for the consumer. The exercise focused on the human health and safety and not the health of the animals, which makes sense and is the reality. However, for the animal health sector, the attention is focused on the prevention of animal diseases, which was not addressed during the exercise.”

(2) “The exercise did not represent what we truly understand as “animal health” but focused on public health and food safety. Perhaps because of this, the contribution of the animal health sector was perceived as more limited. [...] Previous exercises of this type have included the construction of a surveillance system for the disease in question and it has worked to boost the participation of this sector.”

(3) “Our [animal health sector] involvement in these scenarios compared to other sectors is always somehow minor, perhaps due to the fact that it is very rare to find the original source of such outbreaks in domestic animals.”

It is worth noting that in some countries, animal health and food safety operate under the same institution and work closely together, while in others these sectors operate separately. The results of the evaluation survey conducted at the end of the exercise showed that the majority (91%) of animal health sector participants stated that they had a better understanding of what other sectors expect from them. As such, the results of the post-exercise evaluation survey, together with the online interviews, suggest that the exercise contributed to forming connections between the animal health and the other sectors (4, 5).

(4) “Animal health representatives are now invited to meetings where people from the food and public health sectors also participate.”

(5) “We [as animal health sector] have experienced a stronger communication with the public health sector. Now, at the local level, we call each other when outbreaks occur, we exchange information,

Overall, the exercise resulted in relevant cross-sectoral work and discussions. One of the most positive aspects of SimEx highlighted by interviewees was the large representation of actors from different sectors, something that is not always achieved in simulation exercises. Moreover, meeting face-to-face with the different participants allowed for the establishment and/or strengthening of interpersonal relationships between professionals from all sectors (6 – 8). This, in turn, may facilitate the development of communication between different authorities and stakeholders, where necessary, in the event of future challenges or threats. In addition, it became apparent that participants learned about the need to work more closely together and gained a greater awareness of the role that other actors from different sectors could play and the potential challenges that could arise (9).

(6) “We are not used to working in a team where we must involve all sectors, so defining the different roles and functions was something new to us. Bringing different actors together in the same room to discuss a common topic made the exercise very useful and helped to identify barriers and needs.”

(7) “Participants at regional level from the public health and food safety sectors did not know each other [before the exercise] and are now collaborating on different matters.”

(8) “The exercise was a very good opportunity to meet colleagues and experts from different sectors face-to-face and be able to exchange contacts.”

(9) “[After the exercise] it has become clearer to everyone who does what.”

Although some of the interviewees experienced increased communication with other sectors, many countries have not yet reached this point. Therefore, to ensure this continuity, establishing a routine of meetings with representatives from different sectors should be considered a priority for countries seeking to implement and follow a One Health strategy.

In line with this, the idea of creating a nationally coordinated team with an action plan including harmonised protocols, tools, and databases emerged from the interviews. There was agreement on the need to form such a team when no major crisis is under investigation, which would help maintain continuity and ensure a rapid response to potential emergency situations. The team would need a common language and terminology to achieve a coordinated plan of action, where all actors can participate, and good communication can be guaranteed. To this end, when planning simulation exercises in the future, the development of complementary materials with common insights and terminology could be considered. One participating country has positive experiences of this practice.

4. Impact of the exercise and actions taken by the participating countries

Following the exercise, participating countries could use the lessons learned to implement or strengthen the One Health approach. To achieve this, a key point highlighted by SimEx was the need to strengthen capacities and harmonise approaches to data exchange between key health stakeholders. Consistent with this, it would also be important to overcome legal constraints to the implementation of cross-sector data sharing. However, most countries lack plans to develop and implement data exchange platforms to ensure inter-institutional communication.

Another major challenge appeared to be the lack of political support from top of office (10). In the interviews, there was a widespread perception of the need to show governments and policy makers the value of the One Health approach to help implementation. It was widely agreed that partnerships should first be initiated at the local and regional level. This way, governments, institutions, and other decision makers could see the benefit of having these collaborations and pursuing the One Health perspective. Moreover, it is important to note that the involvement of the governmental level would be essential to harmonise procedures and establish standards across different regions.

To mitigate this possible political blockage and to achieve genuine improvements at the national level, consideration should be given to involving actors in higher positions (e.g., competent authorities such as Ministries of Health and Agriculture) in simulation exercises (11, 12). This could contribute to direct the discussion towards resources, budget, or infrastructure, as well as decision-making capabilities and needs (13). Such aspects could also be discussed with other parties, such as private companies (14).

(10) “In our country, if we want to implement a One Health approach, we are still missing political will.”

(11) “When it comes to outbreak investigations, the decisions are taken at a higher level, and, unfortunately, those were marginally involved [in the exercise]. Thus, it would be crucial to include them in this kind of exercises, even if it seems a real challenge.”

(12) “Information must flow throughout the organisation, and, in our case, this [flow of information] was lacking during the exercise. The apical level, which is the one taking action, was never involved.”

(13) “There were times during the exercise when decisions needed to be taken, and one of the biggest questions that emerged was: who is going to pay for this?”

(14) “Private companies should not be overlooked as important actors [in One Health implementation].”

Involving the apical level of the competent authorities may be a challenge, but consideration should be given to readapting an exercise in which they play some role in parallel to the operational technical teams working on outbreak investigations daily. In this regard, exercises such as SimEx can be of great value in supporting and strengthening networking capacities, while contributing to inform decisions for action and build arguments and motivation for pursuing a One Health approach.

In addition, to have an impact on the implementation of the results, dissemination is crucial. In this regard, most countries have plans to publish a summary of the main conclusions, results and recommendations derived from the exercise, addressed to different actors of the national and international community. These dissemination activities take different formats, such as official national documents or reports, scientific publications in international scientific journals or conferences, as well as the organisation of meetings with different stakeholders to share lessons learned, perspectives, and plans for collaboration.

For countries that already operate under the One Health approach and have well-established organisational systems, these exercises continue to be very well received and the interest and need to support them has become apparent. As mentioned above, simulation exercises such as SimEx offer a major opportunity to form new collaborations and channels of communication, as well as to maintain good practice and protocols in those times when no emergency situations are happening, presenting an opportunity for preparedness and anticipation (15).

(15) “Participating in such an international exercise was an opportunity to assess where we stand [as a country] in the field of outbreak investigation in comparison to other countries, as well as to learn from them.”

5. Future perspectives – planning on future simulation exercises

Based on the lessons learned and the experiences of the participating countries, some future support in the practical implementation of One Health through different initiatives could be considered.

Firstly, given the organisational differences between countries, the adaptation of such exercises to their individual situation is needed to achieve the necessary structure for the One Health approach. To this end, internal organisation, structures, and working language are important factors to be considered.

Secondly, a different approach that came up during the interviews is to conduct national after-action review exercises of a past real situation (16). This could be valuable in overcoming the specific challenges that countries are currently facing, as well as implementing and/or improving their response frameworks and organisational structures. Drawing on external European experts and facilitators could help to identify gaps in their systems. Furthermore, it would contribute to building

on and learning from real situations and challenges involving key debates, lines of communication, and decision making. The latter seems to be the most challenging part to overcome when it concerns the development and implementation of actions. Thus, some Member States, while aiming to follow the One Health approach, are still far from having an action plan to achieve their goal (17).

(16) “The scenario was well presented but the actual outbreaks have more challenges to address. Most countries are aware of the "One Health" approach, but may encounter organisational obstacles, for example to protect industry or other commercial interests. Therefore, working on real challenges to be improved and identifying weaknesses would be of high value.”

(17) “After the exercise, no specific changes have been observed. In general, there is a growing awareness towards the One Health approach, but we are still at the stage of talking and not acting. For this, someone needs to lead the change.”

6. Final remarks

Overall, actors in the included European countries showed a willingness and readiness to adopt, if they have not already done so, the One Health approach by working and collaborating more closely with other sectors. To this end, institutional support and training will be crucial to further develop such simulation exercises at local, regional and/or national level, in order to reinforce messages and sustain partnerships. Therefore, investment in prevention, contingency, and capacity building should certainly remain a high priority.

Appendix II: Guidelines for the evaluation of the final Joint Integrative Project (JIP) reports and the SimEx Project report, based on D3.9

General information on the One Health European Joint Programme (EJP) is available on the website OneHealthEJP.eu.

For more insight into the guidelines for project leaders to report on their Joint Integrative Project (JIP), deliverables D4.1 “Instructions for Project Leaders’ reporting on Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs), excl. final reporting” and D4.12 “Instructions for final reporting of JIPs”, should be consulted. Guidance for the WP3 and WP4 Team to monitor the Joint Research Projects (JRPs) and JIPs, respectively, is described in deliverable D3.5 “Guidelines for WP3/WP4 to monitor projects (at start, periodic and end-term evaluations)” (all public deliverables are available on www.onehealthejp.eu/deliverables).

The current procedure details the evaluation process of the JIP final reports by evaluators external to the One Health EJP consortium. It is based on D3.9 “Guidelines for the evaluation of the final JRP reports” and the updated “Guidelines for the evaluation of the final JRP reports, based on D3.9” developed by WP3 in collaboration with WP4 and takes into account the final reports expected in June 2020.

	Proposal writing		Project		
PL JRP	D3.3 Submission		D3.1 Reporting	D3.1 Reporting	D3.1 Reporting
PL JIP	D3.3 Submission		D4.1 Reporting	D4.1 Reporting	D4.12 Reporting
WP3 / WP4			D3.5 Monitoring	D3.5 Monitoring	D3.5 Monitoring
Experts		D3.6 Evaluation proposal			D3.9 D4.19 Evaluation final report

– Contact details of the One Health EJP WP4 team and the Support Team

The Support Team may be contacted for general questions related to this procedure. Detailed research related questions should be forwarded to the WP4 team.

- One Health EJP Support Team: Arnaud Callegari and Lucyna Haaso-Bastin, Email: ohjpcoord@anses.fr
- One Health EJP WP4 Team (Joint Integrative Projects): Karin Artursson, Email: karin.artursson@sva.se, ohjpc@sva.se

– Role of the One Health WP4 team

Project leaders submit their final reports according to the instructions laid out in D4.12 “Instructions for final reporting of JIPs”. The WP4 team will then administer their evaluation. Its role is as follows:

- To remind projects leaders to submit their final report according to the guidelines and using the appropriate template which will be sent out to PLs;
- To verify that the self-assessment in which the project leader compares the project outcomes with the initial objectives as described in the full proposal (see further) has been appropriately dealt with;
- To contact external experts and stakeholders or “end users” for the evaluation of the final reports following the current procedure, and to collect the evaluation forms;
- To transfer the evaluated final reports and accompanying documents (e.g. evaluation sheets) to the Support Team at ANSES;
- To disseminate the final reports to the Project Management Team, the Scientific Steering Board, the External Scientific Advisory Board and the Research Executive Agency.

Identification of External Experts for Evaluation

The final reports will be evaluated by external evaluators who are recognized experts in the fields of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats. Contact will be sought with at least one of the experts that evaluated the project’s full proposal and with one additional expert, based on the existing list of experts (D3.6 “Updated guidelines for Evaluation of proposal + Selection of projects (JRP&JIP)”, see [website](#)). The experts must not currently be engaged in or have had close collaboration with the project leader or deputy leader of the One Health EJP project in the past 5 years prior to the submission of the final report, i.e. as from June 2015 for reports submitted in June 2020.

In addition, one Programme Owner Committee (POC) representative (i.e. “end user”, e.g. experts from ministries or regional food agencies) will be invited to assess the general outcome of the project, i.e. the integration among consortium partners, the One Health efforts and impact of the project, including on the longer term (project sustainability). POC members are per definition not independent from the One Health EJP beneficiaries and will therefore not be invited to sign a “No Conflict of Interest” document.

Scientific experts and Programme Owner Committee representatives will be contacted and invited to register through an online questionnaire (see further).

Each report will thus be evaluated by three experts (i.e. two scientific and one stakeholder expert).

The evaluation process for the OHEJP exercise SimEx will principally follow the same procedure as for JIPs. The nomination of experts will be based on advice from the SimEx Advisory Board.

– Evaluation process

The WP4 team will invite the scientific experts and the Programme Owner representatives to the evaluation process. The email will include:

- a short description of the One Health EJP with a link to the website OneHealthEJP.eu
- the following information relevant for the assessment of the JIP reports:
 - ✓ a hyperlink to the webpages of the projects for which the final report needs

evaluation;

- ✓ a hyperlink to the procedures for project leaders to report on JIP (D4.1 “Instructions for Project Leaders’ reporting on Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs), excl. final reporting” and D4.12 “Instructions for final reporting of JIPs”);
 - ✓ these guidelines for the evaluation of the final reports;
 - ✓ specifically for the external expert who initially assessed the project full proposal, that evaluation form will be attached to the mail;
- a hyperlink to an online registration form “Registration as evaluator of final reports for One Health EJP”. This form includes a “Confidentiality Agreement” statement (Annex A) and information regarding protection of personal data, GDPR (Annex B).

For the evaluation of the SimEx Project report relevant documents that will be provided are

- ✓ these guidelines for the evaluation of the final report;
- ✓ the SimEx Project directive;
- ✓ the SimEx Project plan;
- ✓ the “Confidentiality Agreement” statement (Annex A) and information regarding the protection of personal data, GDPR (Annex B).

The selected experts (both for JIPs and the SimEx Project) who have successfully registered will receive digital copies of the following documents:

- the project final report(s);
- a confirmation of “No Conflict of Interest” (Annex C) (this does not apply to the POC representatives since they are end users of the One Health EJP outcomes and therefore not independent from the One Health EJP by definition);
- a template to mark the evaluation scores and comments (Annex D for JIPs and Annex E for the SimEx Project report).

Each scientific expert will have to send a scanned copy of the signed “No Conflict of Interest” document (Annex C) to ohelj@sva.se prior to evaluating the report. In case of a conflict of interest, the external expert is excluded from the evaluation process, and she/he will be asked to destroy the received documents.

– **Criteria for evaluation**

For the **SimEx Project report** evaluation, the criteria to be assessed and the scoring scheme can be found in Annex F.

For the **JIP report** evaluation, the following criteria will have to be assessed according to the scoring scheme below. The criteria are:

- Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal: How well do the project outcomes meet the initial objectives of the project? Is any deviation justified?
- Scientific excellence and/or quality of the outcome: Did the project deliver sound and scientifically qualified results with progress beyond the state-of-the-art, following the proposal initially submitted? Did the multi-disciplinary, complementary approach between the consortium partners deliver successfully?
- Quality and efficiency of the implementation: In general, was the project management appropriate? Evaluation of the effectiveness of the measures taken to exploit and

disseminate the project results, to communicate on the project, and to manage data.

- Integration: Was the project successful in achieving relevant integrative activities (i.e. improved capacity building, development of harmonized protocols, joint strains and biobank collections, joint databases, harmonized surveillance strategies, addressing legal aspects of general interest) that will allow partner organizations to further improve harmonization or alignment in order to better support their prevent-detect-response tasks? Has sufficient attention been paid to cross-sector collaboration and alignment (One Health aspect)?
- Sustainability: Will developments achieved by the project be maintained within the organizations of the consortium (procedures as well as capacities, collections or databases, etc.)? Will other institutes be able to take on board (some of) the results?
- Impact of the project: Will the impact of the project last over a long period of time? Are the project outputs of relevance for national and/or international stakeholders? Are the project outcomes likely to have positive secondary effects such as economic benefits, e.g. more efficient governing, facilitated communication between public health/ animal health/ food safety authorities.

The external evaluators will assess the report as follows:

1. To score all criteria providing whole numbers from 0 to 5, which leads to a maximum score of 30;
2. To comment on each criterion in a few lines; this will help to give feedback to both the project leaders and the Scientific Steering Board.

The duly filled in evaluation form (Annex D) must be sent back to ohelp@sva.se before the deadline.

For the external evaluation of the OHEJP exercise SimEx the evaluation form Annex E should be used.

0	Weak	The report shows severe imperfections for the criterion under examination. The criterion is not addressed or cannot be judged due to missing or incomplete information.
1	Poor	The results show that insufficient progress was made for the criterion under examination or it was addressed in an inadequate manner. The report shows serious weaknesses for this criterion.
2	Good	The report broadly addresses the criterion under examination; however, the outcome is moderate. The results are rather average of what could have been expected.
3	Very good	The report addresses most of the criterion under examination well; however, the expected outcome could be better.
4	Excellent	The outcome of the criterion under examination is of high quality or the results related to that criterion are excellent.
5	Outstanding	The outcome of the criterion under examination stands out with exceptional novelty, innovation or progress of science at a global level.

– Discussion of the evaluation reports (JIP)

WP4 team will present the evaluation reports to the Project Management Team including the OHEJP scientific leader, the Scientific Steering Board, the EC (REA), and the External Scientific

Advisory Board members who are in charge of the high-level follow up of the One Health EJP outcome.

The SimEx Project evaluation report will be included in deliverable D4.30 “Final report SimEx and evaluation report” due in M63.

– **Annexes**

– **Annex A. Confidentiality Agreement**

Although the final project reports are public deliverables, One Health EJP documents such as mails, letters, evaluation forms, etc. regarding the evaluation of the projects are confidential and should therefore be handled and stored with due care and confidentially.

Experts are therefore not allowed to disclose any information concerning project documents or evaluations to outsiders, nor are they allowed to use this confidential information to their own benefit or anyone else’s benefit or disadvantage. In addition, they may not reveal to outsiders (including the partners of the project) that they are assessing reports of a particular researcher. Anyone who has questions about the project documents or evaluation reports shall be advised to contact ohjep@sva.se.

Once the evaluation has been completed, experts are requested to destroy all project documents and any copies made of them. Confidentiality must be maintained until all valorizations of the outcomes are completed (e.g. publications).

I hereby confirm that I have read and accepted the Confidentiality Agreement.

Name of expert:

Date:

Signature:

Please send a scan of the duly filled in and signed document to: ohjep@sva.se

– **Annex B. Protection of personal data (GDPR regulation)**

Information concerning the protection of the expert's personal data

The One Health EJP organises the online registration of evaluators at Sciensano, Brussels, ["Registration as evaluator of final reports for One Health EJP"] to identify experts in the field of the One Health EJP and to facilitate their assignment to a reading panel that will evaluate reports.

The online tool collects personal data of candidate experts and includes questions on their availability and their expertise.

If the expert agrees to participate in the evaluation process, he/she needs to sign the consent form.

Objective of the registration tool

The aim of this online tool ["Registration as evaluator of final reports for One Health EJP"] is to facilitate the assignment of the experts to one or more reports for evaluation. Its outcome will only be used for this particular purpose.

Reimbursement

If the expert decides to review One Health EJP reports, he/she will be reimbursed a fee of €225 for evaluating 2 final reports (i.e., the actual fee for experts working for the EC, which equals €450 reimbursement for 1 working day). The actual fee to be paid will be calculated pro rata for the number of reports read, i.e., €112.25 per report.

Confidentiality

The expert's data will be stored for use by Sciensano. The expert's identity who has participated in the evaluation may also appear in official One Health EJP documents, which will be validated by the EC (Research Executive Agency) and become public. Sciensano will not reveal the identity of the experts per project. This process is conducted in accordance with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of May 25, 2018. The expert can access his/her collected data at any time.

Concerning the protection of the expert's personal data

The information requested will be used in accordance with the permission the expert has given to the Belgian law of 30 July 2018 concerning the protection of individuals in relation to the use of personalized data and the European regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and the Council of 27 April 2016 (in place since 25 May 2018) concerning the protection of people in relation to the use of personalized data and the free flow of data (GDPR).

If the expert decides to fill in his/her personalized data in the online tool, he/she confirms to have gone through these privacy conditions.

The personal data Sciensano collects in the online registration tool is the following

- The expert's first name and family name
- The organization for which the expert works
- The country where the expert works
- The expert's professional e-mail
- The expert's availability in a defined period of time

Sharing the expert's data

The expert's data will be shared with Hein Imberechts (Sciensano, BE), Pikka Jokelainen (SSI, DK), Karin Artursson (SVA, SE), Manuela Caniça (INSA, PT) and Arnaud Callegari (ANSES, FR) who support and supervise the evaluation process of the project reports (JRPs and JIPs, see www.OneHealthEJP.eu for details). Involved administrative support functions may also share the data.

Saving and protecting the expert's personal data

The expert's data will be saved in electronic form (LymeSurvey, csv table).

Sciensano will save the expert's personal data until the end of the One Health EJP project, September 2023.

The expert's choice regarding his/her personal data

The expert has the right to ask Sciensano whether his/her data were used. He/she may ask to rectify and delete the data, he/she can oppose the further use of the data or limit the use of the data. All requests have to be motivated.

To do this, the expert will have to write a formal request in which is specified what he/she wants to know, rectify or delete. This request has to be dated, signed and accompanied by a copy recto-verso of the expert's ID-card, together with contacting details. If the conditions are fulfilled, Sciensano will in the shortest delays honour the request and inform the expert about it.

How can the expert contact us?

For questions regarding the use of personal data by Sciensano in the framework of the One Health EJP tool, the expert can contact us:

Sciensano

Juliette Wytsmanstraat 14

1050 Elsene

Belgium

T. : +32 2 642 51 11

F. : +32 2 642 50 01

info@sciensano.be

www.sciensano.be

The Sciensano service Data Protection and the Officer for Data Protection can be contacted by email at dpo@sciensano.be.

The expert also has the right to file a complaint about how his/her data have been handled to the Belgian supervising authorities responsible for the legal aspects regarding the protection of personal data. This service can be contacted at:

Data protection authority

Rue de la Presse 35

1000 Brussels

Belgium T. : + 32 (0)2 274 48 00

F. : +32 (0)2 274 48 35

contact@apd-gba.be

Additional information

Additional information about this study can be obtained from the scientific One Health EJP coordinator via email (ohbjp@sciensano.be) or telephone (+32 477 911 050).

Please confirm that you agree with the protection of data by signing the following form:

I hereby confirm that I have read, understood and approved the information form regarding the protection of my personal data. I have had enough time to think, and I have been able to ask all the questions that have come to mind. I understand that if I have more questions or concerns about the use of my personal data, I can contact Sciensano (details mentioned above).

I agree with the regulations concerning the protection of personal data as explained above, the fact that my personal data as expert who has participated in the evaluation of project report will be used by Sciensano and that my identity may also appear in official OneHealth EJP documents, which will be validated by the EC and eventually become public. Sciensano will not reveal the identity of the experts per project.

Name of expert:

Date:

Signature:

Please send a scan of the duly filled in and signed document to: ohjep@sciensano.be and ohjep@sva.se

– **Annex C. Confirmation of No Conflict of Interest**

External Experts are requested to declare any actual or potential conflict of interest towards the project documents. Disqualification may be essential for a number of reasons:

- If the expert:
 - was involved in the preparation of the final report that she/he is invited to evaluate;
 - is a director, trustee or partner or is in any way involved in the management of the project(s) she/he is requested to evaluate;
 - is employed or contracted by one of the beneficiaries involved in the project;
 - has close family ties or other close personal relationship with the leadership of the project (the project leader or deputy leader of the project, WP Leaders, etc.);
 - has (or has had during the last five years) a scientific collaboration with the project leader or deputy leader of the project;
 - has (or has had) a relationship of scientific rivalry or professional hostility with the leadership of the project (the project leader or deputy leader of the project, WP Leaders, etc.) for a period of three years;
 - has (or has had), a mentor/mentee relationship with the leadership of the project (the project leader or deputy leader of the project, WP Leaders, etc.);
- If the approval or rejection of the project report may in any way benefit or harm the expert personally.

Disqualification will also be inevitable if their impartiality may otherwise be endangered, or if they feel that they have a conflict of interest.

In case of a possible conflict of interest the person must notify ohjep@sva.se without any delay.

I hereby confirm that I do not have a conflict of interest.

Name of expert:

Date:

Signature:

Please send a scan of the duly filled in and signed document to: ohjep@sva.se

– Annex D. Template for the evaluation of joint research project (JRP) and joint integrative project (JIP) reports

Project title or acronym:
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	0 Weak	1 Poor	2 Good	3 Very good	4 Excel- lent	5 Out- standing
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal						
Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach						
Quality and efficiency of the implementation						
Integration						
Sustainability						
Impact of the project						

Total score (max 30):

Remarks (please include at least one comment per criterion)

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the full proposal:
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Scientific excellence and/or innovative approach:
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Quality and efficiency of the implementation:
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Integration:

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Sustainability:

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Impact of the project:

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Please send a scan of the duly filled in and signed document to: ohjep@sva.se

– **Annex E. Template for the evaluation of the SimEx project report**

Evaluator:

The evaluation concerns the entire SimEx project, not individual countries (or comments concerning some countries), for all criteria.

	0 Weak	1 Poor	2 Good	3 Very good	4 Excel- lent	5 Out- standing
Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the Project Directive						
Innovative approach						
Quality and efficiency of the implementation						
Integration						
Sustainability						
Impact of the project						

Total score (max 30):

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Remarks (please include at least one comment per criterion)

Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the Project Directive:

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Innovative approach:

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Quality and efficiency of the implementation:

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Integration:

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Sustainability:

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Impact of the project:

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Please send a scan of the duly filled in and signed document to: ohjep@sva.se

– **Annex F. Criteria for evaluation of the Simex project report**

For the report evaluation, the following criteria will have to be assessed according to the scoring scheme below. The criteria are:

- Alignment of the results with the project objectives as set out in the Project Directive: How well do the project outcomes meet the initial objectives of the project? Is any deviation justified?
- Innovative approach - quality of the outcome: Did the project deliver sound and qualified results, following the Project Directive? Did the multi-disciplinary, complementary approach between the consortium partners deliver successfully?
- Quality and efficiency of the implementation: In general, was the project management appropriate? Evaluation of the effectiveness of the measures taken to exploit and disseminate the project results, to communicate on the project, and to manage data.
- Integration: Was the project successful in achieving relevant integrative activities that will allow partner organizations to further improve harmonization or alignment in order to better support their prevent-detect-response tasks? Has sufficient attention been paid to cross-sector collaboration and alignment (One Health aspect) within countries?
- Sustainability: Will developments achieved by the project be maintained within the organizations of the consortium? Will other institutes be able to take on board (some of) the results?
- Impact of the project: Will the impact of the project last over a long period of time? Are the project outputs of relevance for national and/or international stakeholders? Are the project outcomes likely to have positive secondary effects such as economic benefits, e.g. more efficient governing, facilitated communication between public health/ animal health/ food safety authorities?

The external evaluators will assess the report as follows:

1. To score all criteria providing whole numbers from 0 (low) to 5 (high), which leads to a maximum score of 30;
2. To comment on each criterion in a few lines; this will help to give feedback to both the project leader and the Scientific Steering Board.

The duly filled in evaluation form, Annex E, has to be sent back to ohjep@sva.se before the deadline.

0	Weak	The report shows significant imperfections for the criterion under examination. The criterion is not addressed or cannot be judged due to missing or incomplete information.
1	Poor	The results show that insufficient progress was made for the criterion under examination or it was addressed in an inadequate manner. The report shows significant weaknesses for this criterion.
2	Good	The report broadly addresses the criterion under examination; however, the outcome is moderate. The results are only average, considering what could have been expected.
3	Very good	The report addresses most of the criterion under examination well; however, the expected outcome could be better.
4	Excellent	The outcome of the criterion under examination is of high quality or the results related to that criterion are excellent.
5	Outstanding	The outcome of the criterion under examination stands out with exceptional novelty, innovation, preparedness or progress of science/concept at a national or international level.